

Trees Outside Forests: options for certification of sustainable management.

Gerry Lawson MICFor MIBiol

Research Fellow, Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, Edinburgh, UK
Forest Translation, Calle Morera 5, Castillo de Bayuela, Toledo 45641, Spain

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1 SUMMARY

This report was commissioned to explore the sustainable management criteria and operational requirements which could be used for Trees Outside Forests, with an emphasis on agroforestry and urban trees. During write-up, the PEFC Task Force supervising this work recommended that a single generic set of criteria and requirements should be developed, covering the three categories of Tree Based Systems (TBS): forests, agroforests and urban trees. The wording “Trees Outside the Forest” (ToF) has been retained in this report until further guidance is obtained from the PEFC.

The seven criteria used in the PEFC Sustainable Forest Management Meta-standard have been retained, although several of the Requirements were found to be repetitive and have been excluded. It is expected that there will be significant changes to this Meta-standard as part of a review currently being undertaken by the PEFC, and parts of this report could be restructured following these changes.

The main conclusions are:

1. The current FAO definition of ToF does not identify the true resource of ToF, since: a) “forest” is defined using a single threshold of 10% crown-cover that is not appropriate for all countries, b) areas of “Other Wooded Land (OWL)” are excluded despite the fact that they are defined as “non-forest”; c) areas smaller than 0.5ha are excluded; d) areas of shrub with no trees can be included as ToF since they are classed as “Other Land with Tree Cover”; e) rules on excluding agroforestry on forest land are unclear. Had OWL been included in the total for ToF in the 2015 FAO Forest Resource Assessment, the ToF area would have increased from 5.18% to 27.14% of the global area of “tree-based systems”.
2. The ToF statistics requested by the FAO Forest Resource Assessment were provided only by 78 out of 234 countries. However, the World Agroforestry Centre concludes that 43% of agricultural land worldwide has at least 10% tree crown-cover, and this points to the need for greater effort to quantify the ToF resource.
3. GHG emissions from Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) will be reported from 2023 onwards by many more countries than is currently the case. Countries are expected to follow IPCC methodology and categorise their entire land surface into forest, cropland, grassland, settlements, wetlands and other. Each country will therefore be required to clarify its national definition of “forest” land, within the thresholds permitted by the Marrakesh Accords of the UNFCCC. For Annex 1 countries (43 in total) it is likely that very-high-resolution (VHR) satellite images and GIS systems will be developed to contain the boundaries and ownership details of all forest and agricultural parcels, together with (some) information on isolated trees and trees at parcel boundaries. These IPCC “Tier-3/Approach-3” GIS systems are an ideal basis for individual owners, or groups of owners, to plan the management of ToF systems.
4. Very-high-resolution GIS systems do not yet exist for the great majority of non-Annex 1 countries (154 in total), and they face major challenges in defining and mapping parcel boundaries and ownership. There are difficulties and costs in obtaining the necessary orthoimages of land use and tree cover, but remote sensing coverage is improving rapidly. A driver for this is climate change reporting — including calculation of REDD+ baselines and biannual UNFCCC GHG reporting. There may be scope for recognition of traditional land titles to be linked to ToF land management plans, and further studies could be undertaken by the PEFC. Identification of both land and tree tenure is crucial for the development of simplified ToF management plans in these countries.
5. The existing SFM Meta-standard is used here to define a generic ToF meta-standard, with small additions relating to: a) use of Good Agricultural Practice standards when appropriate, b) recognition of carbon sequestration functions, c) recognition of air pollution filtration role of urban trees; and d) recognition of potential role of all trees in reducing some non-CO2 greenhouse gases. It would be possible to quickly modify these guidelines into a generic “Tree Based Systems Meta-standard”.

6. Initial suggestions and literature references have been included in “Draft Guidelines” for sustainable management of agroforests and urban trees, with the former structured separately for UNFCCC Annex 1 and non-Annex 1 countries. These Draft Guidelines need expansion and refinement..

2 TERMS OF REFERENCE

This report responds to a request from Sarah Price, PEFC Head of Projects and Development on 29th April 2016 to:

Report on how the PEFC Sustainable Forest Management Standard (PEFC Council 2010) might be adapted to give criteria and operational requirements applicable to Trees Outside the Forest (ToF) and to make recommendations to the Working Group revising the PEFC Standards, and in particular the Task Force considering certification of Trees Outside Forests. Specifically:

- A. Report on criteria/requirements which could be used for agroforestry (e.g. in Europe), ready for discussion at the PEFC Sustainable Forest Management Working Group (WG1) on 9-11th May.*
- B. Develop a questionnaire for ToF task-group members to use from 21st July onwards, with initial “suggestions” for revised wording of requirements.*
- C. Synthesise responses to the questionnaire, and other feedback, into a report to the Task Force by the end of August 2016. The suggested wording should be appropriate for both agroforestry and urban-forestry.*

3 INTRODUCTION

Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) has received much interest worldwide (Köhl & Rametsteiner 2007). In Europe, Criteria and Requirements for SFM have been created at both national and European levels (Baycheva et al. 2013; Forest Europe 2015). Forest certification in Europe has been successful, with 103 million hectares certified by 2014, or 57.7% of the total area of forest and other wooded land in the EU28. 37.5% is contributed by national certification schemes which are recognised by the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification schemes (PEFC) and 20.2% in certificates recognised by the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) (UNECE 2015).

Task A initially focused on the situation in Europe and generated the following outputs:

- A short paper titled “Sustainable Management Criteria for Agroforestry in the European Union (Lawson, Brunori, et al. 2016b) was included in the proceedings of the 3rd European Agroforestry Congress“ (Gosme 2016), and made available to the Task Force (TF).
- A more detailed analysis of changes needed in the PEFC Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) Meta-standard (PEFC ST 1003:2010) to accommodate agroforestry systems is available (Lawson, Brunori, et al. 2016a)
- A presentation on the above paper, given by Antonio Brunori of PEFC Italy is also available (Brunori 2016) – it discusses implications of the criteria and requirements on both agroforestry and urban trees.

Task B was met by 15/7/16 when a [Google Sheet](#) was circulated with draft Criteria and Requirements for ToF. Seven TF members commented on these in tabs on the Sheet. Recommendations were discussed at a webinar on 25/8/16.

The remainder of this report addresses Task C, and reflects the conclusions of the TF webinar that:

1. replacement of “Forest Management” with terms like “Agroforestry Management” and “Urban Tree Management” is unnecessary and “ToF” is preferred in almost all instances;
2. some of the suggested wording was too prescriptive and should be replaced by more neutral language appropriate to Standards;
3. replacing “forest” with “ToF” resulted in some requirements which were too onerous for small-scale farmers, and greater use was needed of caveats like “appropriate to scale, intensity and risk”;

4. a separate Meta-standard for ToF was unnecessary-- and the existing SFM Meta-standard could be reworded to make it generic and applicable to both ToF and Forests;
5. there were two ways of making the existing Meta-standard generic: a) simply adding a note that “when ‘Forest Management’ or ‘Forest’ are mentioned, this should be read as applicable to ‘Trees Outside Forests’; b) rewording and simplification should be attempted using a generic phrase like “**tree systems**” or “**tree-based systems**”;
6. either of the approaches in (5) should be accompanied by Guidelines giving issues to be considered when applying the requirements to agroforestry or urban trees.

The term “Tree-Based Systems” has been used in numerous publications (Minang et al. 2011; Plieninger et al. 2012/1; Willemen et al. 2013; Rivest et al. 2013; Reynolds et al. 2007; Luedeling et al. 2014; Place et al. 2016) as a collective phrase for forestry, agroforestry urban forestry systems. It is not used here but would have significant advantages if accepted by the PEFC.

4 FOREST & ToF DEFINITIONS

Extending the scope of Sustainable Forest Management certification (PEFC Council 2010) to **trees outside forests** (PEFC 2015; de Foresta et al. 2013) clearly requires common understanding of the meaning of “forest”. There are three ways of doing this: a) a unified international definition applying to all countries, b) flexibility for countries to set their own definitions within a range of internationally agreed limits, c) countries continue using their own categorisation of forest v agricultural land, independently of internationally agreed limits.

- A. **Internationally agreed threshold values in the forest definition:** the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) Forest Resource Assessment gives a single definition of forest based on minimum area, % crown-cover and minimum potential tree height;
- B. **Internationally agreed RANGE of threshold values in the forest definition:** the UNFCCC Marrakesh Accords set minimum and maximum limits for the three criteria above, and countries notify the UNFCCC Secretariat with the values that they will use for climate change reporting related to forests;
- C. **National classifications of land use based on historical or subsidy criteria.** In many UNFCCC-Annex 1 countries a complete national rural cadastre exists, and the tax paid by a landowner depends on whether a land parcel is classified as forest or agriculture. This categorisation also affects the market value of the land, and management methods which a landowner can use. The cadastral classification of a parcel as forest or agriculture matters much more to a landowner than how it is reported by national agricultural departments to the FAO or UNFCCC.

4.1 FAO Forest Resource Assessment

The FAO Global Forest Resources Assessment (FRA) is produced every five years, and requires countries to report on a range of forest statistics for four mutually-exclusive land use categories: Forest, Other Wooded Land, Other Land, Inland Water. These categories are expected to cover 100% of land.

The FRA defines “**forest**” (FAO 2015a) as:¹

*land spanning more than 0.5 ha hectare with a cover more than 10% and trees higher than five metres, or trees able to reach those thresholds in situ, it does not include land that is **predominantly** under agricultural or urban land use.*

The following clarification is provided by the FAO.

¹ The UN Convention on Biological Diversity definition is very similar (CBD n.d.): “A land area of more than 0.5 ha, with a tree canopy cover of more than 10 %, which is not primarily under agriculture or other specific non-forest land use. In the case of young forest or regions where tree growth is climatically suppressed, the trees should be capable of reaching a height of 5m in situ, and of meeting the canopy cover requirement”.

1. Forest is determined both by the presence of trees and the absence of other predominant land uses. The trees should be able to reach a minimum height of 5 metres.
2. Includes areas with young trees that have not yet reached, but which are expected to reach, a canopy cover of at least 10 percent and tree height of 5 metres or more. It also includes areas that are temporarily unstocked due to clear-cutting as part of a forest management practice or natural disasters, and which are expected to be regenerated within 5 years. Local conditions may, in exceptional cases, justify that a longer time frame is used.
3. Includes forest roads, firebreaks and other small open areas; forest in national parks, nature reserves and other protected areas such as those of specific environmental, scientific, historical, cultural or spiritual interest.
4. Includes windbreaks, shelterbelts and corridors of trees with an area of more than 0.5 hectares and a width of more than 20 metres.
5. Includes abandoned shifting cultivation land with a regeneration of trees that have, or are expected to reach, a canopy cover of at least 10 percent and tree height of at least 5 metres.
6. Includes areas with mangroves in tidal zones, regardless whether this area is classified as land area or not.
7. Includes rubberwood, cork oak and Christmas tree plantations.
8. Includes areas with bamboo and palms provided that land use, height and canopy cover criteria are met.
9. Excludes tree stands in agricultural production systems, such as fruit tree plantations, oil palm plantations, olive orchards and agroforestry systems when crops are grown under tree cover. Note: Some agroforestry systems such as the “Taungya” system where crops are grown only during the first years of the forest rotation should be classified as forest.

Two further categories were used in the FAO Forest Resource Assessment² from 1990 onwards (MacDicken 2015):

Other Wooded Land (OWL), which is *“land not defined as Forest”, spanning more than 0.5 hectares; with trees higher than 5 metres and a canopy cover of 5-10 percent, or trees able to reach these thresholds; or with a combined cover of shrubs³, bushes and trees above 10 percent. It does not include land that is predominantly under agricultural or urban land use.”*

Explanatory notes for OWL: the definition has two options - a) the canopy cover of trees⁴ is from 5-10% and the trees should be higher than 5m or able to reach 5m in situ, b) the canopy cover of trees is less than 5% but the combined cover of shrubs, bushes and trees is more than 10% - this includes **areas of shrubs and bushes where no trees are present**. b) includes areas with trees that will not reach a height of 5m in situ with a canopy cover of 10% or more (e.g. some alpine tree vegetation types, arid zone mangroves etc); c) includes areas with bamboo and palms, provided that land use height and canopy cover criteria are met.

“Other Land with Tree Cover (OLTC)”, which is *“land considered as ‘other land’,⁵ that is predominantly agricultural or urban lands use and has patches of tree cover that span more than 0.5 hectares with a canopy cover of more than 10 percent of trees able to reach a height of 5 meters at maturity. It includes both forest and non-forest tree species.”*

Explanatory notes for OLTC. a) The difference between Forest and Other Land with Tree Cover is the land use criteria. b) OLTC Includes groups of trees and scattered trees (e.g. trees outside forest) in agricultural landscapes, parks, gardens and around buildings, provided that area, height and canopy cover criteria are met. c) . Includes tree stands in agricultural production systems, for example in fruit plantations and agroforestry systems when crops are grown under tree cover. Also includes tree plantations established mainly for other purposes than wood, such as oil palm plantations. d) Excludes scattered trees with a canopy cover less than 10 percent, small groups of trees covering less than 0.5 hectares and tree lines less than 20 metres wide.

Both OLTC and OWL could be regarded as “Trees outside Forest”, but:

- A. both have an area threshold of 0.5ha and therefore smaller groups or lines of trees are excluded;

² The **forest** definition has significantly changed since the first FAO international forest assessment. For instance in its 1968 World Forest Inventory, FAO defined “forest land” as “all land with a ‘forest cover’, that is with trees whose crowns cover more than 20% of the area and that is not used primarily for purposes other than forestry” (Husch 1968).

³ **Shrub** for the FAO is a woody perennial plant, generally more than 0.5 m and less than 5 m in height at maturity and without a definite crown. The height limits for trees and shrubs should be interpreted with flexibility, particularly the minimum tree and maximum shrub height, which may vary between 5 m and 7 m

⁴ **Tree** for the FAO is a woody perennial with a single main stem, or in the case of coppice with several stems, having more or less definite crown including bamboos, palms, and other woody plants meeting the above criteria. More detail in a European context is available in (Gschwantner et al. 2009).

⁵ The UNFCCC definition of “**other land**” is preferred — i.e. any land that is not forest, agriculture, settlement or wetland. EU Member States have provided lists of non-agricultural activities in rural areas which would be considered as “other land”, e.g. carparks, solar panels playing-fields and airports.

- B. OLTC is the equivalent of ToF for the FAO (Bellefontaine et al. 2002) and their definition therefore includes areas which have exclusively “shrub” cover.

An agroforestry area with “predominant” agricultural use would be considered as OLTC, provided it meets the same area and crown cover criteria as “forest”. If the agricultural use of the agroforest is secondary then the land will be considered as “forest” or “Other Wooded Land” depending on the tree crown cover. This means that most systems of shade coffee or cocoa and other agroforestry crops would be considered as OLTC, as would plantations of oil palm grown primarily for purposes other than wood. Plantations of rubber and bamboo are normally considered as forest however (Buckingham et al. 2014), even though they have often replaced native forests with much higher levels of biodiversity (Keenan et al. 2015). Statistics are collected separately for these two plantation types, and also for mangroves. The decision on whether forest or agriculture is the “predominant” land use is difficult (Chazdon et al. 2016), and also has consequences for potential funding of REDD+ projects, since this applies only to “efforts to **RE**duce **E**missions from **D**eforestation and **f**orest **D**egradation”. REDD+ projects are often seen to encourage agricultural intensification in monocultures, rather than the ecological intensification of multi-strata agroforestry (Mbow et al. 2012).

In the 2015 FRA Other Land with Tree Cover (OLTC) was reported on by 78 of the 234 countries, and represented 5.18% of total “tree based systems” (i.e. Forest + OWL + OLTC) in 2015 (Table 1). Forest represented 72.87% of the area, and Other Wooded Land (OWL) 21.95%. If OWL is considered as “outside the forest” (which it is by definition) then a more complete definition of ToF is OLTC + OWL, or 27.14% of the total tree-based system area.

Table 1: Overall Statistics from the FAO Forest Resource Assessment in 1990, 2000, 2005, 2010 and 2015. Data abstracted from FAO Databases. Other Land With Tree Cover (OLTC) is assumed by the FAO to be “Trees outside Forests”. Areas are in thousand ha.

FRA	Countries	Forest Area	OthWoodLand	OthLand	OLTC	Land Area	Countries OLTC	Forest%	OWL%	OLTC%
TOTAL 2015	234	3,999,134	1,204,471	7,845,172	284,262	13,048,777	78	72.87%	21.95%	5.18%
TOTAL 2010	234	4,015,673	974,163	7,412,851	280,080	13,047,706	76	76.20%	18.49%	5.31%
TOTAL 2005	234	4,032,743	953,692	7,420,089	267,949	13,047,113	74	76.75%	18.15%	5.10%
TOTAL 2000	233	4,053,582	954,448	7,397,928	253,315	13,045,347	70	77.04%	18.14%	4.81%
TOTAL 1990	233	4,128,269	978,454	7,298,290	247,080	13,044,703	65	77.11%	18.28%	4.62%

De Foresta et al (2013) confirmed that, for the FAO, ToF included “Trees, bamboos, palms, shrubs and bushes found in “Other Lands” (i.e. not including OWL) and recommended the introduction of three subclasses, with a minimum size threshold of 0.05ha — i.e. 500 m². (Figure 1):

ToF-AGRI: i.e. all lands predominantly under an agricultural use with trees and/or shrubs, whatever their spatial pattern (in line, in stands, scattered), provided that the area is ≥ 0.05 ha, the canopy cover is $\geq 5\%$ if trees are present, or $\geq 10\%$ if combined trees, bushes and shrubs, the width ≥ 3 m and the length ≥ 25 m.

ToF-URB: i.e. all lands predominantly under an urban use with trees and/or shrubs whatever their spatial pattern (in line, in stands, scattered), provided that the area is ≥ 0.05 ha, the canopy cover is $\geq 5\%$ if trees are present, or $\geq 10\%$ if combined trees, bushes and shrubs, the width ≥ 3 m and the length ≥ 25 m.

ToF-NON A/U: i.e. all lands not predominantly under agricultural or urban use, with either a) small tree stands ($0.05 \leq \text{area} < 0.5$ ha), with canopy cover $\geq 5\%$ if trees are present, or $\geq 10\%$ if combined trees, bushes and shrubs. Or b) narrow linear tree formations, ($3 \text{ m} \leq \text{width} < 20 \text{ m}$), with canopy cover $\geq 5\%$ if trees are present, or $\geq 10\%$ if combined trees, bushes and shrubs.

These subcategories aim to provide both maximum and minimum thresholds for ToF. The minimum threshold is important to quantify “ToF” as a land use category. Clearly a one hectare field with one tree in the middle of it should not be classed as agroforestry or “ToF land”. Management of the tree itself could still use agroforestry practices (e.g. high pruning, ploughing at base to manage rooting), but the field would not be an agroforestry system. A parcel with many boundary trees, like bocage in Normandy (Figure 2), would be primarily agricultural and therefore classified at ToF-Agri, but what is the area involved: is it the whole agricultural field, or just the hedge (presuming it is bigger than 0.05ha)? Hedges with trees are a vital part of the agricultural landscape in many parts of the world. In Europe they would often be classified as “landscape features” and would be counted within the agricultural land area of the farm, and would be eligible for

agricultural area-based subsidies. Farmers will lose out if these thin strips or clumps of trees start to be classified as “forest”.

The 2015 Forest Resource Assessment did not adopt the recommendations of de Foresta *et al* above, and continued to report only on areas of Other Land with Tree Cover exceeding 0.5ha (FAO 2015a). It is not clear whether the ToF subdivisions in Figure 1 (with minimum areas as small as 0.05ha) will be requested for the 2020 FRA. Many countries will not have remote sensing capable of reporting at this resolution, and deciding whether the land is “predominantly agriculture” is difficult without ground truth surveys.

More information on the quality of forest inventory data used in individual countries is available in their online FRA 2015 reports, and through the three-tier quality assessment made by most countries, for around one third of the variables reported on. This is similar to the Tier system used by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (see next section) and uses the following codes: Tier 1 (expert estimate), Tier 2 (low intensity or incomplete surveys, older data) or Tier 3 (high reliability, recent sources with national scope).

Figure 1: Suggested classification of “Trees outside Forests” for use in the Forest Resource Assessment 2015. This assumes that ToF is present only in “Other Land” and not within the “Other Wooded Land” category. (de Foresta *et al.* 2013)

Figure 2: A typical bocage-agroforestry landscape in Normandie, France. Since the boundary trees are not in blocks > 0.5ha they are unlikely to be reported as ToF in the FAO Forest Resource Assessment (de Foresta *et al.* 2013)

In addition to recommending that the FRA should record three ToF Subclasses, de Foresta *et al* (de Foresta *et al.* 2013) also recommended the following.

1. National ToF assessments should be carried out --- particularly because of the importance of ToF for three international conventions (UN-FCCC, UN-CBD and UN-CCD).
2. The future role of ToF in the FRA other FAO inventories should be clarified, in particular:
 - a. By reining definitions of terms in the FRA 2015 (e.g. agricultural use, urban use, and abandoned shifting cultivation) so that is is clearer where the frontier between Other Wooded Land and Other land With Tree Cover,
 - b. By increasing the number of countries reporting OLTC, and
 - c. By developing a global ToF assessment using the FAO FRA Remote Sensing Survey (FAO 2016).⁶
3. FAO should organise an expert consultation to refine the seven themes suggested in Table 2 as a basis for ToF resource assessment.

Table 2: *The seven FRA 2010 themes, their associated variables, and their proposed equivalent for a future global ToF Assessment (de Foresta et al. 2013).*

Themes for FRA 2010	Proposed themes for a global TOF assessment
Extent of forest resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area of forest • Growing stock of forests • Forest carbon stock in living biomass 	Extent of TOF resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area with TOF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Area with TOF on agricultural land ◦ Area with TOF on urban land ◦ Area with TOF on non urban/non agricultural land • Growing stock of TOF • Carbon stock in living TOF biomass
Forest biological diversity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area of primary forest • Area of forest designated primarily for conservation of biodiversity • Area of forest within protected areas 	TOF biological diversity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area of TOF systems with high biodiversity value such as agroforests and agroforest parklands • Number of tree species involved in TOF systems
Forest health and vitality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area of forest affected by fire • Area of forest affected by insects (and diseases?) 	TOF health and vitality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area with TOF affected by fire • Area with TOF affected by insects and diseases
Productive functions of forest resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area of forest designated primarily for production • Area of planted forest • Total wood removals 	Productive functions of TOF resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total wood removal from areas with TOF • Total non wood removal from areas with TOF (by category: fruit, gum latex and resin, leaf, bark)
Protective functions of forest resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area of forest designated primarily for protection of soil and water 	Protective functions of TOF resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area with TOF ensuring protection of soil and water
Socio-economic functions of forests <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area of forest under private ownership • Value of total wood removals • Employment in primary production of goods 	Socio-economic functions of land with TOF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area with TOF under private or/and community ownership • Area with TOF under State ownership • Value of total wood removals from TOF • Value of total non-wood removals from TOF • Employment in primary production of goods from TOF
Legal, policy and institutional framework <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest area with management plan • Human resources in public forest institutions • Number of students graduating in forestry 	Legal, policy and institutional framework <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area with TOF under disputed ownership status • Human resources in public institutions dealing with TOF • Number of students graduating in agroforestry and in urban forestry

It would be very useful to know the FAO response to the above recommendations? ToF is hardly mentioned in the draft “FAO Voluntary Guidelines on National Forest Monitoring and Assessment (NFMA)”. Sections I & II of these guidelines (covering “the definition of NFMA, the scope and the principles”) do say that ToF “should be included within the term Forest Resources” (FAO 2014), but the draft of Section III (covering “compilation of good practices and technical recommendations on NFMA”) (FAO 2015b) merely says that

⁶ This covers the Earth’s whole land surface and has about 13,500 10km x 10km samples, of which about 9,000 are outside deserts and areas with permanent ice This grid of sample plots is the same as used for the national forest assessments supported by FAO and by many national forest inventory programmes. Landsat images (from around 1990, 2000 and 2005) were interpreted and classified using an automated supervised approach. Nearly 7 million polygons were analysed at each time interval to enable detection of forest area, forest gains and forest losses **5 hectares** or greater in size.

countries should decide for themselves whether ToF is included in their monitoring or not. There is seems to be no attempt to standardise the approach to ToF monitoring, or even to discuss the issue?

However, one of the few estimates of the production of ToF uses the NFMA data for 11 countries across three continents. For six of these, more than 10% of the national above-ground tree biomass was accumulated outside forests (Schnell, Altrell, et al. 2015).

While the FRA 2000 had a whole chapter devoted to Trees Outside the Forest, by the FRA of 2015 this had reduced to a box, with the following content:

While not technically considered as forest, according to the standard forest definition used by FAO and many other international organisations, trees outside forests are a valuable source of many products and services found in forests. In some countries they provide critical supplies of wood, fruits and other non-wood forest products. For FRA 2015 the area of trees outside forests was reported to be 280 million ha in 2015, which is an increase from the 246 million ha reported for 1990; however, only 84 countries, representing 51 percent of global forest area, reported on this variable.⁷ While substantially more difficult and costly to measure than forest at a national level, trees outside forests are clearly an important natural resource in many countries.

As argued above, a more logical definition of ToF would be the sum of Other Wooded Land (which by definition is not “Forest”) and “Other Land with Tree Cover”. In the 2015 FRA this represents 1,489 million ha, or 27% of the total area of Tree Based Systems.

It is therefore a very hard task to identify all areas of ToF. Indeed the FAO stipulation that TOF should have a minimum area of 0.5 ha and a crown cover of 10% means that there are actually three types of tree: Trees In Forests (TiF), Trees outside Forests (ToF) and Trees outside Trees outside Forests (ToToF) (Finlayson 2013)!

Even in the European Union, where there has been significant harmonisation of agricultural policies, there is no consensus on the threshold tree densities or crown-covers within a parcel, which should define “agroforestry”. Agricultural departments in EU Member States were asked by the European Commission to provide both a maximum and minimum number of trees/ha for plantations which would be considered as “agroforestry” (Lawson 2016), but few have done so. Even when the MS Rural Development plans do give “tree” number thresholds per ha, they do not specify the size or age at which a seedling or sapling becomes a “countable tree” — leading to much confusion in the implementation of policy (Brannen 2016).

Schnell et al (2015) reviewed the efforts being used worldwide to quantify ToF resources with remote sensing and recommended against the complex FAO “area-based” approach (Figure 1) They suggested that national TOF inventories should use subsamples based on high resolution images, supplemented by Lidar where possible, and measure all trees above an agreed dbh or crown diameter threshold. The number and volume of trees would be reported using the 3 land use categories suggested by the FAO — i.e. urban, agriculture and “natural formations”. This approach also matches the Indian definition of ToF as “all those trees, which have attained 10 cm or more dbh on land which is not notified as forests” (FSI 2015). It could be used alongside the records of “landscape-feature” trees and tree-rows held by EU Member States, where the threshold tree crown-diameter is set as 2 metres (Luketić et al. 2015).

In summary, we have seen that FAO FRA have very rigid definitions of “forest” and “ToF” which may be useful for international comparisons, but do not assist land classification in individual countries or complete quantification of ToF. The following sections explore other approaches which may be more appropriate.

4.2 UNFCCC - National Inventories of GHG Emissions and Removals⁸

The definition of forest in the UNFCCC Marrakesh Accords (UNFCCC/CP/2001/13/Add1) is :

⁷ Note from Table 1 that in 2015 only 78 countries gave non-blank or non-zero figures for “Other Land With Tree Cover (OLTC)”, not the 84 given here. See discussion elsewhere on whether OLTC is an acceptable surrogate for ToF.

⁸ Annual inventories of emissions and removals of direct GHGs (carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), perfluorocarbons (PFCs), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆) and nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃)) from 4 sectors: (a) Energy; (b) Industrial Processes and Product Use; (c) Agriculture Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU), and (d) Waste, for all years from the base year (or period) to two years before the inventory is due.

Forest is a minimum area of land of 0.05-1.0 hectares with tree crown-cover (or equivalent stocking level) of more than 10-30 per cent with trees with the potential to reach a minimum height of 2-5 metres at maturity in situ. A forest may consist either of closed forest formations where trees of various storeys and undergrowth cover a high proportion of the ground or open forest. Young natural stands and all plantations which have yet to reach a crown-cover of 10-30 per cent or tree height of 2-5 meters are included under forest, as are areas normally forming part of the forest area which are temporarily unstocked as a result of human intervention such as harvesting or natural causes but which are expected to revert to forest.

Countries which are signatories to Annex 1⁹ of the UNFCCC are required to report the thresholds which they have set for “forest” within the permitted ranges for the three key criteria (area, %crown-cover, tree height). This enables a country-specific distinction between forest land and agricultural land (reported in UNFCCC terms as “cropland” or “grassland”). The other 3 land-use categories used in UNFCCC reporting are wetlands, settlements and other.

Table 3 shows the forest definition criteria selected by most Annex I countries for UNFCCC reporting. Only 6 EU Member States¹⁰ from 28 use the FAO criteria (0.5ha, 10% crown-cover, 5m potential height) in full. Only Norway of the 13 non-EU Annex I countries (with available data) uses the FAO criteria.

⁹ Each Party included in Annex I shall, for the purposes of applying the definition of “forest” as contained in paragraph 1 (a) above, select a single minimum tree crown-cover value between 10 and 30 per cent, a single minimum land area value between 0.05 and 1 hectare and a single minimum tree height value between 2 and 5 metres. The selection of a Party shall be fixed for the duration of the first commitment period. The selection shall be included as an integral part of its report to enable the calculation of its assigned amount pursuant to Article 3, paragraphs 7 and 8, in accordance with decision 19/CP.7, and shall include the values for tree crown-cover, tree height and the minimum land area. Each Party shall justify in its reporting that such values are consistent with the information that has historically been reported to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations or other international bodies, and if they differ, explain why and how such values were chosen.

¹⁰ Italy is one of the six EU-MS which implements FAO criteria at a national level, but is considering a reduction in the minimum area to 0.2ha and an increase in canopy cover to 20% (Pisanelli pers comm).

Table 3: Minimum values for area, tree crown-cover and potential tree height as specified by UNFCCC Annex I countries. EU data is from the European Commission (2013a), and other countries from Lund (2016). EU Member States which follow the FAO thresholds are marked with an asterisk.

MINIMUM VALUES FOR FOREST AREA SIZE, TREE CROWN COVER AND TREE HEIGHT FOR UNFCCC ANNEX 1 SIGNATORIES							
EU Countries from Annex V In Decision No 529/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council 21 May 2013				Other Annex 1 Countries. Lund (2016). Links in Table.			
EU Member State	Area (ha)	Crown Cover (%)	Tree height (m)	Other country	Area (ha)	Crown Cover (%)	Tree height (m)
Austria	0,05	30	2	Australia	0.2	20	5
Belgium	0,5	20	5	Belarus	0.1	30	
Bulgaria	0,1	10	5	Canada	1	25	5
Cyprus				Croatia	0.1	10	2
Czech Republic	0,05	30	2	Iceland	0.5	10	2
Denmark*	0,5	10	5	Japan	0.3	30	5
Estonia	0,5	30	2	Lichtenstein			
Finland*	0,5	10	5	Monaco			
France*	0,5	10	5	New Zealand	1	30	5
Germany	0,1	10	5	Norway	0.5	10	5
Greece	0,3	25	2	Russian Federation	0.5	30	5
Hungary	0,5	30	5	Switzerland	0.0625	20-60	3
Ireland	0,1	20	5	Turkey	3	10	5
Italy*	0,5	10	5	Ukraine	0.1	30	5
Latvia	0,1	20	5	USA	0.37	10	5
Lithuania	0,1	30	5				
Luxembourg*	0,5	10	5				
Malta							
Netherlands	0,5	20	5				
Poland	0,1	10	2				
Portugal	1,0	10	5				
Romania	0,25	10	5				
Slovakia	0,3	20	5				
Slovenia	0,25	30	2				
Spain	1,0	20	3				
Sweden*	0,5	10	5				
United Kingdom	0,1	20	2				

Developing countries are not signatories to Annex 1 of the UNFCCC, but if they wish to be eligible for afforestation projects in the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) of the Kyoto Protocol they are also expected to provide country-specific values for the three criteria (Table 4).

Note that only 4 (Cambodia, Philippines, South Korea, Togo) of the 55 non-Annex I countries which have registered their forest definitions with the UNFCCC use the FAO “standard” of 10% crown cover, 0.5 ha minimum area and 5m tree potential height *in situ*. It is therefore possible that many countries are reporting “forest” area in successive FRAs using their national definitions rather the FAO “standard”.

Table 4: Parameters used in the definition of Forest supplied to the UNFCCC by non-Annex 1 Countries, in order to be eligible for CDM afforestation projects. Full details are available on the UNFCCC CDM website¹¹.

Country	Minimum Crown Cover (%)	Minimum Area (ha)	Minimum Tree Height (potential in situ)
Albania	30	0.1	3
Argentina	22.5	1	3
Azerbaijan	20	0.5	2.5
Belize	30	0.3	5
Bolivia	30	0.5	4
Brazil	30	1	5
Burkina Faso	10	0,05	2
Cambodia	10	0.5	5
Chile	25	0.5	5
China	20	0.067	2
Colombia	30	1	5
Costa Rica	30	1	5
Côte d'Ivoire	30	0,1	5
Democratic Republic of the Congo	30	0,5	3
Dominican Republic	20	0.0629	5
Ecuador	30	1	5
El Salvador	30	0.5	5
Ethiopia	20	0.05	2
Ghana	15	0.1	5
Guatemala	30	0.5	5
Honduras	30	1	5
India	15	0.05	2
Indonesia	30	0,25	5
Kenya	30	0.1	2
Kyrgyzstan	20	0,5	3
Lao People's Democratic Republic	20	0,5	5
Madagascar	30	1	5
Malaysia	30	0.5	5
Mali	30	1	2
Mexico	30	1	4
Mongolia	10	1	2
Morocco	25	1	2
Mozambique	30	1	5
Myanmar	10	0.1	2
Nicaragua	20	1	4
Niger	30	1	4
Pakistan	30	0.05	3
Panama	30	1	5
Paraguay	25	0.5	5
Peru	30	0.5	5
Philippines	10	0.5	5
Republic of Korea	10	0.5	5
Republic of Moldova	30	0.25	5
Rwanda	10	0.05	3
Senegal	30	0.5	2
South Africa	30	0.05	2
Sri Lanka	20	0.05	3
Thailand	30	0,16	3
Togo	10	0.5	5
Trinidad and Tobago	10	0.4	3
Uganda	30	1	5
United Republic of Tanzania	10	0.05	2
Uruguay	30	0.25	3
Viet Nam	30	0.5	3
Yemen	30	0.5	3

The thresholds chosen for crown-cover make a great difference to the area potentially available for afforestation projects (Figure 3). Use of the maximum UNFCCC-permitted crown-cover threshold of 30% was much criticised when the CDM was introduced, since it was seen as enabling areas of sparse natural forest to be classed as “non-forest” and therefore be eligible for new plantations funded through the CDM (Sasaki & Putz 2009; Verschot et al. 2005) Zomer et al. (2007) found that modifying the crown-cover threshold for “forest” from 30% to 10% reduced the worldwide availability of “non-forest” land for afforestation projects from 7.73 billion km² to 2.28 billion km². Zomer et al (2009) also concluded that **43% of agricultural land worldwide has at least 10% tree cover**, with major differences between continents (Figure 4).

¹¹ <https://cdm.unfccc.int/DNA/bak/allCountriesARInfos.html>

Figure 3: Proportion of wooded land classified as “forest” using different % crown-cover thresholds (Fries et al. 1998)

Figure 4: Percentage of agricultural land with tree cover, year 2000 (Zomer et al. 2009)

In preparation for COP21 in Paris, 162 UNFCCC signatories submitted “Intended Nationally Determined Contributions” (INDCs) and 103 of these included some GHG mitigation activities in the agricultural sector (Richards et al. 2015). Many also mentioned the mitigating role of forests and/or agroforestry (Petersen & Varela 2015; UNFCCC 2015). Grassi & Detener (2015) summed the suggested LULUCF/AFOLU projected emissions for 2030 for 72 countries and found that pledged reductions in emissions from the land use sector represent 20-25% of their overall emission reductions.

There are major methodological issues with the INDCs, and all countries will be expected by the UNFCCC to ensure that their pledges and reporting follow the IPCC guidelines (Milne et al. 2003; IPCC 2006; Bickel et al. 2006; Iverson et al. 2014). This will mean improved differentiation between areas of “forest” and those of other land use categories. There are five land uses in the IPCC Guidelines, in addition to “forest” (see above for definition), and agroforestry is mentioned in two of them. Note that the UNFCCC “other” category is largely barren land, and unlikely to be relevant to ToF.

1. **Cropland.** Which includes all annual and perennial crops as well as temporary fallow land (i.e., land rested for one or several years before being cultivated again). Annual crops may include cereals, oils seeds, vegetables, root crops and forages. Perennial crops can include trees and shrubs, in combination with herbaceous crops

- (e.g. **agroforestry**) or as orchards, vineyards and plantations such as cocoa, coffee, tea, oil palm, coconut, rubber trees, and bananas, except where these lands meet the criteria for categorisation as forest land. Arable land which is normally used for cultivation of annual crops but which is temporarily used for forage crops or grazing as part of an annual crop-pasture rotation is included under cropland.
2. **Grassland.**¹² Includes rangelands and pasture land that is not considered as cropland, and systems with vegetation that fall below the threshold used in the forest land category and are not expected to exceed, without human intervention, the threshold used in the forest land category.¹³ The category also includes all grassland from wildlands to recreational areas as well as agricultural and **silvi-pastoral systems**, subdivided into managed and unmanaged consistent with national definitions.
 3. **Wetlands.** Which include land that is covered or saturated by water for all or part of the year, and that is not classified as Forest land, Cropland, Grassland or Settlements. It includes inland organic soils and wetlands on mineral soils, coastal wetlands including mangrove forests, tidal marshes and seagrass meadows and constructed wetlands for wastewater treatment. It also includes reservoirs, natural rivers and lakes (Hiraishi et al. 2014).
 4. **Settlements.** Which includes all developed land, including transportation infrastructure and human settlements of any size, unless they are already included under other categories. This should be consistent with national definitions.
 5. **Other land.** Which includes bare soil, rock, ice, and all land areas that do not fall into any of the other five categories.

The IPCC Guidelines identify three intensity levels (**Approaches**) for the characterisation of land use, and three (**Tiers**) for the calculation of GHG fluxes from these different land uses. The expectation is that UNFCCC parties will gradually move towards higher level Approaches and Tiers, as their expertise and resources improve.

In more detail, taking the case of land use estimation:

- **Approach 1** identifies the total area for each of the 6 land-use categories within a country, but does not provide detailed information on the nature of conversions between these land uses.
- **Approach 2** introduces tracking of a matrix of conversions all the land-use categories.
- **Approach 3** extends the information available in Approach 2 by allowing land-use conversions to be tracked on a spatially explicit basis (i.e. a comprehensive national land-use GIS system).

Recent announcements regarding the incorporation of LULUCF into EU effort sharing on national emissions targets (European Commission 2016; Lawson & de Baets 2016) have confirmed that Member States will move to **Approach 3** by 2020 (the wording expects “... *spatially-explicit land-use conversion data for the identification and tracking of land-use categories and conversions between land-use categories*”) and it is likely that this will be accompanied by location specific modelling approaches to estimate fluxes of GHG on specific parcels - i.e. **Tier 3**. This is the IPCC “high resolution and high accuracy” approach in Figure 5. This commitment is very exciting for European agroforesters since most Member States will have to improve their inventories of trees on agricultural land, and their models of the impact of trees on emissions from grassland and cropland management.

The move to high-resolution/high-accuracy GHG reporting is also causing a recognition that a single international set of criteria for “forest land” (based on thresholds for minimum area, tree height and %crown cover) may be inappropriate. The national criteria in Table 3 will set the overall rules for classification, but in most countries a GIS database already exists where the boundaries of each parcel of land are identified, together with information on the ownership (cadastral systems) and land use (agricultural monitoring systems) — at least to the level of “forest”, “agriculture” and “urban”. These high-resolution spatial databases are ideal for UNFCCC reporting in Annex I countries, even if some of the parcels do not conform

¹² For the Kyoto Protocol this is termed Grazing-Land.

¹³ This land use category includes non-herbaceous perennial species which can be grazed. The EU definition of “permanent grassland and permanent pastures” (Article 4 Regulation N° 1307/2013) is “land used to grow grasses or other herbaceous forage naturally (self-seeded) or through cultivation (sown) and that has not been included in the crop rotation of the holding for five years or more, it may include other species such as **shrubs and/or trees** which can be grazed provided that the grasses and other herbaceous forage remain **predominant**, as well as (where Member States so decide) land which can be grazed and which forms part of established local practices where grasses and other herbaceous forage are traditionally not predominant in grazing areas.

exactly to the three national criteria in Table 3. High or very-high resolution images and GIS systems are available to farmers in most Annex I countries, and could provide base-maps for farmers to produce Simplified Agroforestry Management Plan (SAMPs).¹⁴

Figure 5: UNFCCC Greenhouse Gas Emissions reporting in Europe will increasingly use the more accurate and robust Tier 3 and Approach 3 methodologies (S Rossi et al. 2015).

4.3 Forest definitions in Cadastral Systems

Lund (2016) found national thresholds of tree crown-cover for “forest land” varying from 0% to 80%, minimum areas from 0.05ha to 1ha (with minimum widths from 2.5 m to 50 meters), and potential tree height from 1m to 7m). He listed more than 300 different national forest classifications, and other studies have pointed to the wide range of definitions in Europe (Pulla et al. 2013), and the great variation in forest inventory methodologies (McRoberts et al. 2012).

Thus, while both developed and developing countries have provided thresholds for the three criteria which define “forest land” according to the Marrakesh Accords, a different set of rules may be used for national legal or “cadastral” databases. In the Netherlands, for example, as soon as more than 20 tree seedlings/ha are planted within an agricultural parcel then it has to be listed in the national cadastre as “forest/nature”, with an immediate reduction in land value and rate of tax (Luske et al. 2016).

Thus the national “cadastre” (or similar land register) is the best place to start when looking for the fine detail on whether an individual parcel is classed as forest or agriculture. Cadastral systems exist, at least in part in most UNFCCC Annex 1 countries.

- Australia:

¹⁴ Very High Resolution (VHR) generally means better than or equal to 5 m pixel resolution. The orthophotos used in the EU Land Parcel Identification Systems of Member States to verify agricultural payments, have a pixel resolution of 50 cm (1:5000) or better!

- Canada: most provinces maintain a searchable cadastre showing boundaries of agricultural and forest parcels, e.g. Quebec¹⁵, [Ontario](#) .. and probably most others
- EU: all countries implement a Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) which shows the boundary of farmers fields (reference layer), and the areas used for different agricultural crops (agricultural layer). Any landowner with land which is eligible for agricultural direct payments will make agricultural returns (IACS) which confirm the use of the land in the current year, including areas which are considered as forest and which are not eligible for agricultural payments (Luketić et al. 2015). Many activities are coordinated by the Permanent Committee on Cadastre in the European Union ([ref](#))
- Japan:
- New Zealand: Land Information New Zealand (LINZ) provides a [rural evaluation tool](#) integrating ownership and many other layers of land use and land potential
- Russian Federation:
- Switzerland: a searchable national database with many layers including [land use](#).
- Turkey: forest cadastre and ownership cadastre conducted by different agencies ([ref](#)).
- USA: some States maintain a cadastre showing boundaries, owners and details of land use including agriculture and forestry - e.g. [Montana](#), [Utah](#)

In non-Annex I countries there are also interesting examples of cadastral systems which have been integrated with high resolution imagery of land cover: e.g. in India (Mothi Kumar et al. 2014; NRSC 2016; Rao et al. 2014; Jayaprasad et al. n.d.). The Global Land Cover Facility provides world coverage of vegetation type and tree crown-cover with a 250 m pixel grid (DiMiceli et al. 2011) but for integration with cadastral datasets much higher resolution is required

In Europe the LPIS often holds information on isolated trees, trees in line and trees on groups on agricultural land on farms, together with areas classified as forest for CAP and Cadastral purposes. However, the LPIS is not a complete rural land register, since it only holds returns from farmers and managers of farmland. For a complete rural Cadastre, countries would require to integrate data from National Forest Inventories (NFI). Information on % Forest Cover is available at a pixel resolution of 25m from the Copernicus system (Copernicus Land Monitoring Services n.d.), and NFI data is available through the European Forestry Institute EFISCEN system (Schelhaas et al. 2006).

One EU example of a well integrated Cadastral and Land Use system is the SIGPAC in Spain. Here the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment (MAGRAMA) has been obliged by the European Union Court of Auditors to introduce an automated classification system to make individual parcels with “excessive” tree cover ineligible for agricultural Basic Payments under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Parcels with 0% eligibility are judged to be “forest” for the purposes of the CAP (Figure 6) even if, for the time being, they remain classified as tree pasture in the country’s online forest map (MAGRAMA 2014).

¹⁵ <http://www.cptaq.gouv.qc.ca/index.php?id=231>; <http://mern.gouv.qc.ca/english/department/index.jsp>

Figure 6: Problems of classification of wood pasture in Spain (and many countries of Europe). This shows a scene near Trujillo from the Spanish Land Parcel Identification System (SIGPAC). An automatic algorithm - based on tree crown-cover, slope and bare ground - has been used to calculate the eligibility of each parcel for agricultural direct payments. The parcel in the centre is judged to have 0% eligibility, and is therefore “forest” rather than “agriculture”.

Thus, in summary...

- A. Given the complexity of the forest v agriculture classification, and issues of scale, it is doubtful whether the additional FAO categories of Other Wooded Land or Other Land With Tree provide much value in identifying areas of Trees outside Forests.
- B. The flexibility allowed in UNFCCC reporting for countries to use their own “forest land” thresholds for area, crown-cover and minimum tree potential height (and sometimes minimum width) allows for a much more robust distinction of forest versus agricultural parcels, and has the potential to be merged in a national or regional cadastral land parcel database.
- C. Detailed UNFCCC LULUCF/AFOLU reporting from 2020 onwards will lead to much improved national geospatial systems to distinguish forestland parcels from cropland and grassland.

5 CRITERIA & REQUIREMENTS FOR SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF ToF

“Trees outside Forests” are found in, or at the edges of, agricultural or settlement land parcels. They are outside land parcels defined as forest using the national criteria discussed above.

The *criteria* and *operational requirements* for ToF follow those in the PEFC Sustainable Forest Management Standard (PEFC Council 2010). Numbering of the requirements is comparable between Standards, although there are gaps if redundancy was apparent. A detailed comparison of the two Standards, in relation to agroforestry, is available online (Lawson, Brunori, et al. 2016a). The seven criteria are:

1. Maintenance and enhancement of ToF and their contribution to global carbon sequestration
2. Maintenance of health and vitality of ToF ecosystems
3. Maintenance and encouragement of ToF productive functions
4. Maintenance, conservation and enhancement of biological diversity in ToF
5. Maintenance and enhancement of protective functions of ToF
6. Maintenance of other socio-economic functions and conditions

7. Compliance with legal requirements

These 7 criteria are closely related to the the Themes used in the 2010 FAO Forest Resource Assessment (Table 2).¹⁶ Changes to the criteria and requirements have been made to provide generic wording for ToF rather than Forests. Criterion 1 now mentions “carbon sequestration” rather than “carbon cycle”, and an additional requirement (2.13) has been added to make reference to potential use of existing standards for sustainable agricultural production. Several requirements appear to be redundant, or could be covered by small changes in others.

5.1 Criterion 1: Maintenance and enhancement of ToF and contribution to global carbon sequestration

1.1 Management of ToF should aim to maintain or increase the number, value and diversity of trees in the landscape and enhance the economic, ecological, cultural and social values of the land unit, including soil and water resources [, and carbon sequestration].¹⁷ Full use will be made of related services and tools that support land-use planning and nature conservation.

1.2 Management of ToF shall comprise a cycle of inventory, planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, at a scale appropriate to the resources of the landowner. Social, environmental and economic impacts of management operations can be included, and would form the basis for continuous improvement.

1.3 Inventory and mapping of ToF shall be established and maintained, adequate to local and national conditions, reflecting clear boundaries and tenure rights, and in correspondence with the topics described in this document

1.4 (Redundant - covered in 1.04, 1.02 and 1.03)

1.5 Simplified ToF Management Plans will be elaborated and periodically updated. They will have details appropriate to scale of the area and the resources of owners, potentially including the following topics: ownership details, parcel maps, species choice, management of timber and non-timber products, agricultural cropping/grazing patterns, and operations aimed at environmental protection and amenity.

1.6 A summary information in the ToF Management Plan should be made publicly available, but may exclude confidential business, personal information and other information made confidential by national legislation or for the protection of cultural sites or sensitive natural resource features.

1.7 Monitoring of ToF and evaluation of their management shall be performed periodically, and results fed back into the planning process.

1.8 Responsibilities for sustainable management in ToF should be clear, especially the responsibilities of tenant-farmers, farmers with "customary tenure" and landowners.

1.9 ToF management practices shall safeguard timber, agricultural and other goods and services, by adopting sustainable tree harvesting rates, and by minimising direct or indirect damage to forest, soil and water resources.

1.10 (Redundant - covered in 1.09)

1.11 Any change of land use for ToF should: a) be in compliance with national and regional legislation and include consultation with materially and directly interested persons and organisations; b) avoid negative impacts on threatened (including vulnerable, rare or endangered) ecosystems, culturally and socially significant areas, important habitats of threatened species or other protected areas.

1.12 (Redundant - covered in 1.11)

5.2 Criterion 2: Maintenance of health and vitality of ToF ecosystems

2.1 ToF management planning shall aim to maintain and increase the health and vitality of ecosystems and to rehabilitate degraded lands, whenever this is possible.

2.2 The health and vitality of ToF should be periodically monitored to identify key biotic and abiotic factors that potentially affect health and vitality of trees, including pests, diseases, overgrazing and overstocking, risks of fire, damage caused by climatic factors, air pollutants or management operations.

2.3 (Redundant - covered in 2.02)

2.4 ToF management plans shall specify ways to minimise the risk of degradation of and damage to ToF systems, and management planning shall use policy instruments set up to support these activities.

¹⁶ For example Criterion 1 is better titled “Planning and monitoring of ToF”, and “Criterion 7 could be “Compliance with Legal and Institutional Frameworks”.

¹⁷ Needed since there is currently no mention of carbon in the requirements relating to Criteria 1. Also "carbon cycle" was inappropriate in the previous title since what matters is taking carbon out of the atmosphere for as long as possible - this is the opposite of a cycle.

2.5 ToF management practices shall make best use of natural structures and processes and use preventive biological measures wherever feasible, and economically appropriate, to maintain and enhance the health and vitality of ToF systems. Adequate genetic, species and structural diversity shall be encouraged and/or maintained.

2.6 Lighting of fires shall be avoided, except when strictly controlled and needed to meet the goals of the ToF management unit

2.7 a) ToF management practices should use tree, crop and animal species and provenances that are suited to the site conditions, and use tending, harvesting and transport techniques that minimise damage soil resources and the environment. b) Indiscriminate disposal of oil and non-organic waste should not take place in ToF and any such waste should be collected and stored in designated areas and removed in an environmentally-sensitive manner [suggest that b) is moved to a separate requirement].

2.8 The use of pesticides in ToF shall be minimised, with appropriate alternatives and other biological measures preferred. Any use shall follow WHO Guidelines and the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants 2001 (as amended), prohibiting WHO Type 1A and 1B pesticides, except where no viable alternative is available, and where any use is defined in a Management Standard. National and regional (e.g. EU) standards should also be followed.

2.9 Redundant - merged in 2.08

2.10 Redundant - merged in 2.08.

2.11 The use of pesticides and herbicides shall follow the instructions given by the manufacturer and be implemented with proper equipment and training

2.12 Fertilisers are used in ToF management they should follow guidelines in national or regional definitions of Good Agricultural Practice (GAP)

2.13 Management of agricultural components in a ToF system should follow nationally or internationally approved Good Agricultural Practice (e.g. GAP International or GAEC - Europe)

5.3 Criterion 3: Maintenance and encouragement of ToF productive functions (wood, non-wood, carbon)

3.1 ToF management planning shall aim to maintain the capability of the land unit to produce timber and other goods and services on a sustainable basis.

3.2 Management planning of ToF shall aim for sound economic performance, taking into account available market studies and possible economic value of all relevant goods and services.

3.3 (Redundant - covered by 3.01 and 3.02)

3.4 (Redundant - covered by 3.01 and 3.02)

3.5 ToF management, harvesting and regeneration activities should be carried out in a way that does not reduce the productive capacity of the site, for example by soil erosion or excessive nutrient removal.

3.6 Harvesting levels of wood, non-wood and agricultural products shall not exceed a rate that can be sustained in the long term with due regard to nutrient off-take and the preservation of soil fertility and structure.

3.7 Where it is the responsibility of the landowner/manager, and included in a management plan, the exploitation of non-timber products, including hunting and fishing, shall be regulated, monitored and controlled.

3.8 Adequate infrastructure such as roads, tracks and bridges should be planned established and maintained in ToF areas, to ensure efficient delivery of goods and services while minimising negative impacts on the environment.

5.4 Criterion 4: Maintenance, conservation and enhancement of biological diversity in ToF

4.1 ToF management shall aim to maintain, conserve and enhance biodiversity on ecosystem, species and genetic levels and diversity at landscape level.

4.2 ToF planning, at a level appropriate for the scale, intensity and risk involved, should identify, sustainably manage or conserve ecologically important areas containing concentrations of: (i) protected, rare, sensitive or representative ecosystems such as riparian areas and wetland biotopes; (ii) areas containing endemic species and habitats of threatened species, as defined in recognised reference lists; (iii) endangered or protected genetic in situ resources; and taking into account, (iv) globally, regionally and nationally significant large landscape areas with natural distribution and abundance of naturally occurring species.

4.3 Protected and endangered plant and animal species shall not be exploited for commercial purposes. Where necessary, measures shall be taken for their protection and, where relevant, to increase their population.

4.4 ToF management shall ensure successful tree regeneration either through natural regeneration of seedlings or coppice shoots, or replanting of high quality seedlings or rooted cuttings.

4.5 Species of trees planted in ToF should be those permitted by the national or state forest administration. These are normally native species and provenances, but may be introduced species, provenances and varieties where their potential impact has been assessed and where permission has been provided by the forest administration. The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) guidance on prevention, introduction and mitigation of impacts of alien species that threaten ecosystems, habitats or species, should be followed.

4.6 ToF planting activities that contribute to the improvement and restoration of ecological connectivity with neighbouring woodlands shall be promoted.

4.7 Genetically modified trees shall not be used, at least until the end of 2022 when this position will be reviewed. Note: This restriction has been adopted based on the Precautionary Principle since there is insufficient scientific data on genetically-modified trees and their impacts on human and animal health and the environment are equivalent to, or more positive than, those presented by trees genetically improved by traditional methods, no genetically-modified trees will be used. (Comment - why not earlier).

4.8 ToF management practices shall, where appropriate, promote a diversity of both horizontal and vertical structures such as uneven-aged stands and the diversity of species such as mixed stands. Where appropriate, the practices shall also aim to maintain and restore landscape diversity.

4.9 Traditional management systems that have created valuable ecosystems, such as coppice, and hedgerow management, on appropriate sites shall be supported, when economically feasible.

4.10 (Redundant - covered by 3.05)

4.11 Infrastructure shall be planned and constructed in a way that minimises damage to ecosystems, especially to rare, sensitive or representative ecosystems and genetic reserves, and that takes threatened or other key species – in particular their migration patterns – into consideration.

With due regard to management objectives, measures shall be taken to balance the pressure of animal populations and grazing on tree regeneration and growth as well as on biodiversity.

4.12 Standing and fallen dead wood, hollow trees, old groves and special rare tree species shall be left in quantities and distribution necessary to safeguard biological diversity, taking into account the potential effect on the health and stability of forests and on surrounding ecosystems.

5.5 Criterion 5: Maintenance and enhancement of protective functions of ToF

5.1 ToF management planning shall aim to maintain and enhance protective functions of forests for society, such as protection of infrastructure, protection from soil erosion, protection of water resources and protection from adverse impacts of water such as floods or avalanches.

5.2 Areas that fulfill specific and recognised protective functions for society shall be registered and mapped, and ToF management plans shall take full account of these areas.

5.3 Special care shall be given to ToF operations on sensitive soils and erosion-prone areas as well as in areas where operations might lead to excessive erosion of soil into watercourses. Inappropriate techniques such as deep soil tillage and use of unsuitable machinery shall be avoided in such areas. Measures shall be taken to minimise the pressure of wild and domesticated animal populations.

5.4 Special care shall be given to ToF management practices in areas with water protection functions to avoid adverse effects on the quality and quantity of water resources. Inappropriate use of chemicals or other harmful substances or unsuitable management practices influencing water quality in a harmful way shall be avoided.

5.5 Construction of roads, bridges and other infrastructure shall be carried out in a manner that minimises bare soil exposure, avoids the introduction of soil into watercourses and preserves the natural level and function of water courses and river beds. Proper road drainage facilities shall be installed and maintained.

5.6 Criterion 6: Maintenance of other socio-economic functions and conditions

6.1 ToF management planning shall aim to respect the multiple functions of trees to society, give due regard to the role of ToF in rural development, and especially consider new opportunities for employment in connection with the socio-economic functions of these systems. Note: The stimulation of rural development can be achieved by training and employment of local people and a preference for the local processing of timber and non-wood products.

6.2 (Redundant - implicit in 6.01)

6.3 Property rights and land tenure arrangements shall be clearly defined, documented and established for the relevant ToF areas. Likewise, legal, customary and traditional rights related to the land shall be clarified, recognised and respected. Note: clarification of land tenure may be an incentive for farmers, or groups of farmers, in developing countries, with traditional rights to participate in certification schemes.

6.4 (Redundant - covered by 6.03)

6.5 Adequate public access to ToF areas for the purpose of recreation shall be provided, taking into account respect for ownership and customary use rights, the effects on tree resources and ecosystems, as well as compatibility with other environmental and social functions.

6.6 Sites with recognised specific historical, cultural or spiritual significance and areas fundamental to the basic needs of local communities (e.g. health, subsistence) shall be protected or managed in a way that takes due regard of the significance of the site.

6.7 ToF management operations shall take into account socio-economic functions, especially the recreational function and aesthetic values of the systems. This shall be done in a way that does not lead to serious negative effects on the sustainability of ToF. (repeats other requirements?)

6.8 ToF managers, contractors, employees and landowners shall be provided with sufficient information on sustainable management techniques, and encouraged to keep up-to-date through continuous training, as a precondition for all management planning and practices described in this “ToF Model Standard”.

6.9 Recommendations for good ToF management shall make best use of the expertise of farmers-groups, forest-owners, NGOs and local people.

6.10 ToF management shall provide for effective communication and consultation with local people and other stakeholders relating to sustainable management of mixed tree, crop and animal systems, and shall provide appropriate mechanisms for resolving complaints and disputes relating to management between the operators and local people.

6.11 ToF management shall be planned, organised and performed in a manner that enables health and accident risks to be identified and all reasonable measures applied to protect workers and the public from these, and inform them about preventative measures. Note: Guidance for specifying national standards can be obtained from the ILO Code of Good Practice: Safety and Health in Forestry Work.

6.12 (Redundant - merged in 6.11)

6.13 (Redundant - merged in 6.11)

6.14 The management of ToF shall be based, inter-alia, on the results of scientific research. Management should contribute to research activities and the data collection needed for sustainable production of timber and other ToF products and services.

5.7 Criterion 7: Compliance with legal requirements

7.1 ToF management shall comply with legislation applicable to forest and agricultural land, including nature and environmental protection; protected and endangered species; rights of tenants and commoners; health, labour and safety issues; and the payment of royalties and taxes.

7.2 ToF should be protected from unauthorised activities such as illegal logging, illegal land use, illegally initiated fires, and other illegal activities.

6 ToF GUIDELINES & REQUIREMENTS FOR AGRICULTURAL AND URBAN LAND.

As discussed above, most countries have their own land registration (i.e. “cadastral”) systems, or are aspiring to develop these. Most of these systems classify land into (at least) forest, agriculture and urban land uses, and these are the three categories which Tree Based Systems will be found. They also reflect the categories used for annual national reporting of GHG emissions to the UNFCCC, although this also has categories for “other land ” and “wetland”. The former is unlikely to be relevant for ToF since it is defined as “bare soil, rock, ice, and all land areas that do not fall into any of the other five categories”. Wetlands are relevant however, and are discussed briefly in Section 5.3.

It is again stressed that 189 Parties to the UNFCCC have submitted “Intended Nationally Determined Contributions” to the Secretariat, and almost all quantify Land Use Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) contributions in their national targets (UNFCCC 2015). LULUCF reporting is well understood by parties to the Kyoto Protocol and Annex 1 UNFCCC parties, but the extension to non-Annex 1 parties will create great interest in IPCC methodology (IPCC 2006) in forestry and agriculture departments throughout the developing world, leading to the enhancement of existing geospatial databases distinguishing the categories of forest, agriculture, settlement, wetland and other land.

6.1 ToF in Agriculture.

The planned use of trees on agricultural land is called agroforestry. Some definitions use terms like “woody vegetation”, “woody perennials” and “trees and shrubs” (Lawson 2016), but the definition is often limited to

trees or named shrub species. Article 23 of the EU Rural Development Regulation (1305/2013) (European Commission 2013c) defines it thus:

“Agroforestry” refers to land use systems in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land. The minimum and maximum number of trees per hectare shall be determined nationally, taking account of local pedo-climatic and environmental conditions, forestry species and the need to ensure sustainable agricultural use of the land.”

The second sentence is needed to define the minimum and maximum tree density or crown-cover thresholds which apply to agroforestry, but does not have to be part of the definition. The form used by the UK and Ireland Farm Woodland Forum¹⁸ is more “farmer- friendly”, and is recommended to the PEFC:

Agroforestry is farming with trees. It is a land use system in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land, and where the trees can be inside land parcels or on boundaries (e.g. in hedges).

This definition covers both trees on agricultural land and agriculture on forest land. This distinction is useful in classifying agroforestry systems (Table 5). On forest land, agroforestry can increase system diversity and resilience, e.g. firebreaks or fuel breaks. On agricultural land the trees can be within parcels (silvoarable or silvopastoral systems) or between parcels (boundary agroforestry).¹⁹

Table 5: *A possible Agroforestry Typology for use in Europe, based on the existing classification of Agricultural and Forest land with the Land Parcel Identification Systems of EU Member States (Dupraz et al. n.d.)*

Tree Location	AF System	Official Land Use Classification (Cadastre/LPIS)		
		Forest Land	Agricultural Land	Other Land
Trees within parcels	Silvopastoral	Forest Grazing	Wood pasture Orchard grazing	n/a
	Silvoarable	Forest Farming	Alley Cropping Alley Coppice Orchard - Intercropping	
Trees between parcels	Boundary Agroforestry	Forest Strips	Shelterbelts Wooded-Hedges Riparian-Tree-Strips	
Settlements	Urban Agroforestry	n/a		Home Gardens

Many agroforestry typologies are possible, and the multi-faceted classification in Figure 7 may be better suited to tropical situations.

¹⁸ <http://www.agroforestry.ac.uk/systems/index.html>

¹⁹ In the European Union hedges can be declared by Member States as “Landscape Features”, with a width of up to 8 meters and are still considered as agricultural land, eligible for area-based subsidies.

Figure 7: Classification of agroforestry based on structural, functional, socioeconomic and ecological characteristics (Xu et al. 2013)

The following section gives **Guidelines** on how the criteria & requirements in Section 4 could be applied to Agroforestry. These tables could be expanded into a Wiki or other web-based resource.²⁰

Criterion 1 (Planning and management of ToF).

Req.	UNFCCC Annex 1 Countries ²¹	UNFCCC Non-Annex 1 Countries ²²
1.1	Most Annex I countries have well developed requirements for Forest Management Plans (DG Environment 2013). These are not adapted to ToF, but all EU Member States a high-resolution GIS system for rural land monitoring (at a scale of 1:5000 from 2016) with details of land use and ownership at level of individual parcels. Sometimes, even individual farm trees or small groups of trees will be mapped in a separate GIS layer. This data is available free to landowners (Luketić et al. 2015), and can form the basis of agroforestry management plans. Non-EU countries also have systems where national cadastres are combined with land use codes (e.g. Australia (ABARES 2010)), or are developing these systems e.g. New Zealand (LINZ 2016) & USA (Bureau of Land Management 2016).	Most non-Annex 1 countries have difficulties identifying the forest/non-forest boundary in national forest inventories (Romijn et al. 2012/5). Resolution of global remote sensing data is improving however: e.g. FAO Global Land Cover Network (FAO 2013), FRA Global Remote Sensing Survey (FAO 2016), GLOBCOVER (300 m pixels) (ESA 2010), PALSAR Forest/non-forest map (25 m pixels) (EORC 2016). Calculation of forest reference levels for REDD+ is driving development of forest land databases (Gibbs et al. 2007), but more effort is needed to link with land ownership records (formal or informal) [(Grieg-Gran 2010), and to clarify the extent to which national definitions of “forest” should include agroforestry (Hawthorne & Boissière 2014; Minang et al. 2011). Examples of linking national VHR datasets of forest resources to cadastral (ownership) data are India (NRSC 2016), Brazil (Lu et al. 2012), China (Rabley & Yuen 2009), Tanzania (Hojas-Gascón & Eva 2014).
1.2	Simplified Agroforestry Management Plans (SAMPs) can be expected from farmers in	Many guides exist to forest management of tropical forest: e.g. (International Tropical Timber Organization

²⁰ E.g. <http://www.eurafwiki.eu/>; <http://wiki.awf.forst.uni-goettingen.de/>; <http://www.forestdss.org/CoP/>

²¹ http://unfccc.int/parties_and_observers/parties/annex_i/items/2774.php (43 countries)

²² http://unfccc.int/parties_and_observers/parties/non_annex_i/items/2833.php (154 countries)

	Annex 1 countries, since most will be in receipt of some form of state assistance. Few examples of SAMPs exist yet however, although some governments are considering their introduction in the context of new planting subsidies for agroforestry (Lawson, Balaguer, et al. 2016)	1992), and increasingly these consider both modern technologies (Sayer et al. 1997) and the needs of participatory management (FAO 2004; Cerutti et al. 2008), yet the need for guidelines on management of trees on agricultural land is clear from Figure 4. While SAMPs will be troublesome farmers in non-Annex I countries they could be interested if linked to official recognition of traditional land titles (Toulmin 2009/1; Cotula et al. 2004; Perera 2009).
1.3	See 1.1	See 1.1
1.5	Advice and templates for SAMPs are available from public, NGO and private organisations. Good examples are available from France (AFHAC 2012) and the USA (Gold et al. 2013). The most comprehensive guide to silvoarable systems in Europe was published by Liagre & Dupraz (Liagre & Dupraz 2011).	The World Agroforestry Centre produces a range of practical guides and toolkits on managing agroforestry systems.
1.6	Full open access to SAMPs may be too onerous for farmers in Annex 1 countries, although if the country provides public access to its Land Parcel Identification System portal, then it is straightforward to attach a PDF document	Public access not necessary for participatory forest management plans (including agroforestry areas in forests) and simplified agroforestry management plans, unless (perhaps) linked to the formalisation of traditional land titles.
1.7	Farmers regularly monitor agroforestry trees, since they have easier access than to forest plots. They can spot disease outbreaks quickly, provided they have simple guides (Agroforestry Research Trust 2016).	Same as for Annex 1 countries, but resources for pest control are less, and biological control methods more likely (Schroth et al. 2000).
1.8	In tenanted farms trees are often owned by landowners while the grazing or crops belong to the tenant. Sample management agreements, explaining tenant/landowner rights and responsibilities are available in France (Chambres d'Agriculture 2010) and the USA (Watson & Godsey 2009).	Lack of clear tenure is one of major limits on agroforestry in the tropics, where trees may "belong" to the tribal chief or to the forest department rather than the farmer (Raintree n.d.; Alagba et al. 2012). SAMPs should clarify all ownership issues.
1.9	Final harvest in agroforestry systems will usually have a lower stem density than conventional forestry, and will benefit from an existing infrastructure of farm tracks. In silvoarable systems ploughing will be followed, so soil compaction unlikely to be an issue. Brochures are available explaining the sustainable management of AF systems (Tubex 2015)	Same as for Annex 1 countries. AF systems are often complex multi-strata systems with uneven age upper canopies. Tree harvesting rates are usually sustainable (Rao et al. 2007).
1.11	AF plantations at low densities on agricultural land remain classified as agriculture (except sometimes in countries with rigid legislation like the Netherlands and Germany), and this is a major advantage for the landowner.	The inadequacy in the tropics of a) defining "forest" by a single crown-cover threshold, b) excluding agroforestry and c) equating old growth and "monoculture fastwood" is discussed above, and e.g. in (van Noordwijk 2015).

Criterion 2 (health and vitality of ToF).

2.1	In Annex I countries there is ample	For non-Annex II countries guidelines on managing
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	evidence of the role of agroforestry in increasing biodiversity, and providing structural diversity, for example, by linking blocks of forest in agricultural landscapes (Gosme 2016; Moorhead & David Dickens 2012)	agroforestry in AF systems are available in a number of research papers and reviews (Bhagwat et al. 2008/5; Schroth 2004; Leakey 1999; Griffith 2000)
2.2	See 1.7 and biodiversity indicators for temperate farming systems (Herzog et al. 2012)	See 1.7 and techniques for rapid biodiversity appraisal (Kuncoro et al. 2006)
2.4	Main biotic and abiotic risks to trees in AF are fire, pests, disease, mechanical damage, windthrow, flooding, drought, climate extremes. Avoidance strategies include mixed species/ provenance planting, higher planting densities, regular monitoring for pests by farmers, providing habitat for predators in tree strips, correct species choice, encouragement of deeper rooting, using open agricultural fire-breaks and fuel-breaks areas to limit fire, planning use of trees for flood control (Dupraz et al. n.d.).	Risk avoidance strategies are similar in non-Annex I countries. Diverse AF systems are frequently mentioned as a mechanism for smallholders to adapt to climate risks (Lasco et al. 2014) and meta-studies have shown fewer pest attacks in AF in tropical systems (Pumariño et al. 2015; Rao et al. 2000; Schroth et al. 2000). However this is not always the case, and fungal diseases of understorey crops like coffee cocoa or plantain can be increased by too dense shade (Sileshi et al. 2008; Norgrove & Hauser 2002) .
2.5	Biological control pest control in temperate AF needs more study, but the International Organization for Biological Control recommends that all farmers implement policies where 5% of their Utilized Agricultural Area is covered with natural elements such as lines of trees and herbaceous species (Boller et al. 2004).	Biological control in tropical AF has been attributed to enhanced levels of birds and bats (Maas et al. 2015), ants (Philpott & Armbrrecht 2006), fungi (Maniania 1991), and many other organisms, although the system is hugely complex (Sampaio et al. 2009).
2.6	Prescribed fire may be a valid management technique in AF rangeland areas of some Annex 1 countries - e.g. Southern USA (Karki 2015) and the Mediterranean (Le Houérou 1993).	Early season prescribed fires in tropical agroforestry systems can prevent uncontrolled late-season fires (Sow et al. 2013/2), and can be important in controlling some weed species (Wibowo et al. 1996)
2.7	Tree species and provenance selection options are increasingly limited by pests and disease in temperate countries. Climate change offers risks (Eggers et al. 2007; Fensham et al. 2015) and opportunities (Broadmeadow et al. 2005) in temperate areas. Farmers can be encouraged to experiment with unusual species in part of their plantations. High quality planting stock is vital.	There is much scope for genetic improvement (e.g. through selection and vegetative propagation) of tropical AF trees, including consideration of rooting characteristics (Schroth 1995), phenology (Roupsard et al. 1999), timber quality (Somarrriba & Eduardo 1990), and fruit characteristics (Simons & Leakey 2004).
2.11	Weed control is vital for tree-establishment of temperate AF plantations and good guides are available (Anon 2016; Dupraz & Liagre 2009), spread of weeds into crop alleys from tree strips can be an issue.	Issues are similar in the tropics, but there is greater emphasis on using cover crops for weed control (MacDicken et al. 1996; Erenstein 2003).

2.12	Temperate AF is thought to be a good mechanism to reduce nitrate (Dupraz et al. 2005), ammonia (Bealey et al. 2014) and phosphorus (Allen et al. 2006) losses compared to temperate agriculture. Trees on agricultural soils seldom need fertilisation, but will benefit from applications to adjacent crops and grassland.	Agroforestry can limit the need for fertiliser application in nutrient poor areas, although this must be balanced against water uptake by tree (Shepherd et al. 1995; Sileshi et al. 2014; Szott et al. 1991) .
2.13	Several national and international certificates for Good Agricultural Practices exist in Annex 1 countries: including GAEC in Europe (Angileri et al. 2011) and GAP in the USA (USDA 2016)	The FAO produces a range of papers on Good Agricultural Practices e.g. (Poisot et al. 2007), which should apply also to agroforestry. GlobalGAP is a private sector body that sets voluntary standards for the certification of production processes of agricultural (including aquaculture) products around the globe. Studies are available of its impact on small scale producers (Mausch et al. 2011) , but not specifically on agroforestry, although there are studies on the impact of sustainability certificates on to perennial shade crops like coffee and cocoa (Raynolds et al. 2007)

Criterion 3 (productive functions of ToF).

3.1	Silvoarable systems are often associated with cover crops, and both help to avoid erosion (Panagos et al. 2015) and increase soil carbon (Palma et al. 2014). Carbon is also increased in silvopastoral systems (Kasahun Kitila et al. 2011).	Many studies have shown the sustainability and productivity of tropical agroforestry systems compared to traditional slash and burn or monocultures (Buck et al. 1998; Ehui & Spencer 1993).
3.2	AF can give higher total yields and profits than agriculture. Land Equivalent Ratios of 1.5+ have been reported (Dupraz et al. 2010), and this is a good measurement tool (Keesman et al. 2007). Regular high pruning is vital for quality sawlogs (USDA 2006). Market and non-market benefits to be included in evaluations (J. Palma et al. 2004; Godsey et al. 2009). A “level playing field” is assumed in state incentives for agroforestry, agriculture and forestry.	Good planting stock (Leakey 1987) and regular pruning are also needed in the tropics for highest quality timber (Bertomeu & Roshetko 2007). A good compilation of methods for economic and financial valuation of agroforestry is Alavalapati and Mercer (2006)
3.5	Harvesting and management to preserve soil structure. Continuous cover AF possible (e.g. Dehesa/Montado) but 100% harvest is more likely.	Agroforestry has significant potential for erosion control (Young 1990; Correal et al. 2009), although there are circumstances in which large large leaves can increase the droplet size (and erodability) of throughfall (Armstrong & Mitchell 1988)
3.6	Temperate AF is particularly useful for pollution control in nitrate sensitive areas	The capacity of the root “safety net” of widely-spaced trees in agroforestry systems to

	(USDA 2004; McHugh 2003; Nair et al. 2007; Whitmore & Schröder 2007).	absorb nitrate and other nutrients is well known in both temperate and tropical situations (Cadisch et al. 1997).
3.7	There are many agroforestry-related NTFPs in forests. One is seasonal grazing within forest lands, which is very important in some temperate areas, e.g. Greece (Papanastasis 2009). The FRA in 2010 showed higher values of Non-Wood Forest Products (8.39 million US\$) in Europe than any other continent (FAO 2010).	Domestication and commercialisation of NTFPs is a key activity for many agroforestry research and extension organisations in the tropics (Leakey et al. 1996).
3.8	Agricultural areas in Annex 1 countries generally have adequate road infrastructure.	In non-Annex I areas road infrastructure may be inadequate even in agroforestry areas (Islam et al. 2012).

Criterion 4 (conservation and enhancement of biodiversity)

4.1	See 2.1 & 2.2. Tree cover in many Article 1 countries remains at a very low level and AF will reintroduce landscape and species diversity while maintaining agricultural production (Varah et al. 2013; Bunce et al. 2009; Von Maydell 1995; Tsonkova et al. 2012; Quinkenstein et al. 2009). Mixed species/provenance planting is needed to increase diversity and resilience.	Many publications exist on AF techniques for biodiversity enhancement in the tropics (Atangana et al. 2014; Schroth 2004; Leakey 1999; Anon n.d.; Jose 2012), including guides published by the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD Secretariat 2009) and ICRAF (Kindt & Coe 2005).
4.2	AF is not suitable on all agricultural land! New planting projects are best adopted progressively and experimentally by farmers in Annex I countries. Layout planning for individual farms and groups of farms is possible with maps and models. See Criterion 1.	Taungya is a type of AF which is potentially effective for plantation establishment and biodiversity enhancement on forest land in the tropics. (Jordan et al. 1992; Ros-Tonen et al. 2014; Menzies & Nicholas 1988). Riparian and wetland forest and AF biotypes should be identified in GIS systems since they are reported separately in UNFCCC (Hiraishi et al. 2014), and can have very high GHG emissions. See Criterion 1 for planning and management tools.
4.3	Tree strips in silvoarable systems can improve agricultural habitats for endangered species - e.g. butterflies .	Germplasm collections of endangered AF species have been undertaken (Lengkeek et al. 2005) and vegetative propagation in AF is often successfully used for trees which have unreliable fruiting or seedling growth.
4.4	AF can be regenerated by replanting or using natural regeneration. Grazing control is vital for the latter, and in some areas (e.g. dehesas (Moreno & Pulido	Assisted natural regeneration works well in the tropics alongside perennial AF crops (Evans et al. 2015/6; Ganz et al. 2003; Shono et al. 2007).

	2009)) regeneration benefits from a period of silvoarable cultivation.	
4.5	Given climate change, increasing pest attacks and the open nature of AF plantations, it may be appropriate to allow a wider choice of tree species and provenances than on forest land. Farmers can experiment providing that good and bad results are recorded and disseminated. Most Annex I countries maintain their own lists of invasive alien species which are banned in plantations e.g. in Europe (Beninde et al. 2015).	National and international compendia are available to assist the selection of tree species to match climate, altitude and soil type (Ellis et al. 2005; Orwa 2010). Policy Guidelines are available on invasive alien species (ICRAF 2014; McNeely 2004).
4.6	Boundary agroforestry is important for landscape and ecological connectivity in Annex I countries. In Europe these strips can be up to 8 m wide and still keep agricultural area payments (what about other Annex I countries?). GIS tools exist to design green veins and wildlife corridors - e.g. in the US (Beir 2008) and Europe (Tamás et al. 2014).	Agroforestry corridors between areas of protected forest have also been evaluated in non-Annex I countries like Ghana (Asare et al. 2014), Brazil (de Lima & Gascon 1999), Costa Rica (Kormann et al. 2016) , China (Lin et al. 2008).
4.7	The long period needed for traditional breeding in trees, and increasing pressure of pests and diseases means that use of GM techniques to introduce tolerance may be justified soon (e.g. for Elm (Gartland et al. 2000), Ash (Harper et al. 2016) or the American Chestnut (Powell 2016)). These are important species for temperate agroforestry.	“Improvement” of commercial plantation species will be more contentious than use of GM for disease resistance in species that would otherwise be wiped out (Harper et al. 2016; Ho & Cummins 2005). These issues soon need to be considered by PEFC.
4.8	AF creates structural diversity, and mixed species management is easier at wide-spacing.	See 4.1
4.9	AF is a traditional management system in most Annex I countries (Dupraz et al. n.d.; Agnoletti 2012). Energy coppice with standards is also a form of agroforestry in Europe since SRC is defined as “agriculture”. Management of trees in hedgerows is widely promoted as a source of fuel and/or carbon sequestration (Crossland 2016).	43% of agricultural land has >10% tree cover (Zomer et al. 2009), so AF is clearly a traditional system, especially in the tropics.
4.11	Duplicates 3.8	

4.12	Some dead trees can be retained in silvopastoral systems, as they are in traditional wood pastures, but will be less compatible with machinery in silvoarable systems..	See 4.1
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Criterion 5: (protective functions of ToF).

5.1	AF gives protection against erosion, flooding etc, especially when used with continuous cover cropping. See 3.1	AF is particularly valuable for soil conservation in the dry and humid tropics (Young 1990; Nair et al. 1995).
5.2	Cadastre and land use maps are available for agricultural areas in Annex I countries at high resolution (1:5000 scale) with other layers showing areas with statutory protection. AF planting in Annex I countries can be planned using databases of potential soil erosion (Bentrup & Leininger 2002; Bentrup & Kellerman n.d.).	Management plans should recognise the protective function of existing AF, and maximise this protection for new areas.
5.3	Soil maps and erosion models will help plan AF layout on farms in relation to slopes and streams.	The impact, and potential design, of tropical AF is increasingly modelled using catchment-scale soil and topographic data in GIS (Roose & Ndayizigiye 1997; Delgado & Canters 2011; Wang Si-yuan et al. n.d.).
5.4	Use of chemicals covered by Good Agricultural Practices (see 2.13). AF wildflower strips act and tree roots act as filters for nitrates and other chemicals (Gold et al. 2013).	Synthetic pesticide use tends to be lower in AF than in conventional agriculture. Intercropping of native pesticidal plant species, and their use in crop storage has a long tradition in some parts of the tropics, and is encouraged where possible (Anjarwalla et al. 2013).
5.5	Farm roads and tracks usually exist already. Duplicates 3.8	Duplicates 3.8

Criterion 6 (other socio-economic functions and conditions)

6.1	AF, like forests, has multiple functions and biophysical modelling tools are available to evaluate these (Jhn Palma et al. 2004).	Figure 8 gives a useful overview of the multiple functions of agroforestry & perennial agriculture in the tropics.
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6.3	Important that tenants, farmers & landowners understand ownership roles and responsibilities. See 1.8	In non-Annex I countries a Simplified Agroforestry Management Plan can help to formalise traditional and communal title to land and tree-products. See 1.8
6.5	Public access for recreation to AF will be more constrained than forests, because of potential damage to crops and livestock, but access trails can be planned in the management plan.	Tourist access to open forests and agroforestry is increasingly a revenue source in the tropics.
6.6	Agroforestry (e.g. parklands) in Annex 1 countries are often of high amenity and recreation value and “fundamental to the basic needs of local communities”..	Management Plans for ToF areas in non-Annex 1 countries should recognise any rights for community use and clarify tenure (Fortman 1985).
6.7	Management of AF in Annex I countries should deliver wider socio-economic functions alongside timber and agricultural production (e.g. recreation and aesthetics), especially if landowners are in receipt of Government assistance.	See 6.6
6.8	AF management needs skills which are new for many farmers in Annex 1 countries and needs collation of research and extension knowledge into searchable databases (Burriel & Coche 2016).	National and international research and dissemination agencies need to provide information on AF management in form easily accessible by farmers (Martini et al. 2016).
6.9	AF is a traditional practice in many Annex I countries, but was replaced by agricultural intensification. Ecological intensification in modern AF can sustain agricultural production and provide quality timber (Dupraz et al. n.d.).	Much indigenous knowledge exists on AF systems in non-Annex 1 countries and can be incorporated in advice from national and international extension agencies (Walker & Sinclair 1999).
6.10	Experience has shown that local communities in Annex 1 countries welcome the greater landscape and environmental diversity in agroforestry (Gao et al. 2014; Moreno et al. 2016).	Complaints and disputes regarding management of AF are unlikely in non-Annex I countries, especially when off-farm benefits accrue to communities (Alavalapati & Mercer 2006).
6.11	Tree operations tend to be safer in AF than forestry because of easier access. ILO, National and EU Guidelines for safe working in forestry and agriculture should be followed (Social Europe 2012) .	Follow any appropriate national guideline for forestry or agricultural operations.
6.14	Collaboration between researchers and farmers is vital, and flexibility is needed	There is a long history of participative research on agroforestry in non-Annex 1 countries and guidelines

	in implementation of planting and management grants to allow innovations to be introduced and monitored by farmers (Briggs 2012).	are available (Rocheleau 1991; Jeremy Hagggar et al. 2001; Holden & Joseph 1991).
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Criterion 7 (Compliance with legal requirements).

7.1	Farmers in Annex i countries are not always familiar with legal requirements re trees - e.g. felling licences. Conflicts may exist around management requirements - e.g. between optimum dates for pruning and legal restrictions introduced to protect birds.	Trees outside forest land in non-Annex 1 countries are often not often covered by forest laws, and will come under pressure as forest lands are depleted. This is especially true if farmers do not own the trees (Boakye & Baffoe 2008).
7.2	Legal rights and responsibilities of landowners and tenants should be defined. See 1.8 & 6.6	See section 1.8 and 6.6

Figure 8: Multiple functions of agroforestry systems (Lawson & Dupraz [in prep](#)).

6.2 ToF in Settlements

General points to consider

Criterion 1 (planning and management of ToF).

- 1.1 Management Aims.** Urban and peri urban trees have a long history management in Europe (Forrest & Konijnendijk 2005; van Wassenauer et al. 2012; Nilsson et al. 2005; Oosterbaan & Kuiters 2009; Konijnendijk et al. 2005; Wu 2008) and parts of Asia (Kuchelmeister 1998). The focus

worldwide is principally on amenity and recreation, but there are many other benefits including abatement of pollution (Yang et al. 2005; Jin et al. 2014), passive cooling (Shashua-Bar et al. 2010), efficient water use (Hilaire et al. 2008), nature conservation (La Riccia 2015), timber production (Tyrväinen et al. 2005), sustainable development (Konijnendijk et al. 2004; Carter 1993) and carbon sequestration (Pasher et al. 2014).

- **1.2 Management Process.** Urban soils are typically poor in quality, limited in volume and with restricted rooting environments. There are also problems of pollution and vandalism. Trees are often pruned and pollarded to extreme ways to allow them to co-exist with buildings. These present different challenges to conventional forestry or agroforestry (Konijnendijk et al. 2005; Lawrence & Johnston 2011; Long & Nair 1999).
- **1.3 Inventory Methods.** In Annex I countries, very-high-resolution images at scales of 1:5000 or better can be used to locate individual trees in urban settings and per-pixel algorithms using spectral characteristics, texture and neighbourhood relations (Puissant et al. 2014/2). Tree inventories have been or are being conducted in many cities worldwide, including London (Rodgers et al. 2015).
- **1.5 Management Plans:** urban forest governance involves a wide range of stakeholders but management plans are important, and, as with conventional forestry, can comprise high level strategic plans (~20 yrs), management plans (~5 years) and annual operational plans (van Wassenaeer et al. 2012).
- **1.6 Open Access to Information:** The USDA Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) rural forest inventory (USDA Forest Service 2016a) is being expanded to hold results from the Urban Forest Inventory and a data mart (*UrbanDataMart*) is provided to run custom queries. GIS data such as this in Europe will be covered by the Inspire Directive and should be available open access.
- **1.7 Monitoring and Evaluation:** urban expansion is monitored accurately by most Annex 1 countries. A report on 32 European countries shows that this is increasing at 1.7% per year. Bi-annual UNFCCC reporting of LULUCF/AFOLU emissions from 2020 onwards is likely to encourage Annex 1 countries to make regular assessments of green areas in settlements, and sequestration capacity of urban trees (Pasher et al. 2014).
- **1.8 Clarification of Responsibilities.** Identification of who is responsible for potential damage from the roots of trees and real or perceived safety issues can make urban trees a legal minefield (Knuth et al. 2005).
- **1.9 Setting Allowable Harvests.** Urban trees are underexploited for timber harvesting, often because of poor silviculture, which neglects pruning and leads to safety problems in older trees (Vogt et al. 2015). Existing management guides (Roloff 2016) and experience should be disseminated more widely. Statistics are hard to obtain however (Bratkovich et al. 2014). Most timber in the periurban area of non-Annex I countries will go for fuelwood or charcoal (Arnold et al. 2003), particularly in Africa
- **1.11 Limiting Land Use Change.** Urban land use change is determined by the expansion of settlements and is outside the scope of these guidelines, but tree planting and management in urban and peri urban areas is important in stopping this expansion leading to “soil sealing” (EEA n.d.), and complete loss of environmental services.

Criterion 2 (health and vitality of ToF).

- **2.1 Managing for Ecosystem Health.** Urban trees have a huge role in the ecosystem health of settlements (Shackleton et al. 2015; Alvey 2006; Li et al. 2005), and for regeneration of degraded urban land.
- **2.2 Monitoring Ecosystem Health.** Urban trees often grow in hostile environment (salt, wind, poor soils, soil-sealing, flooding, root damage) but regular monitoring of health is helped by easy access (Berrang et al. 1985).
- **2.4 Risk avoidance.** Attack from pests and diseases is increasing following climate change, and urban trees are often most at risk (Tubby & Webber 2010). Techniques are well developed to survey urban trees and identify those that may represent a safety risk (Pokorny et al. 2003).
- **2.5 Natural system resilience.** Adequate species and genetic diversity is important in urban trees, and this lack of diversity can assist devastating disease attacks on species like elm or plane (Blankart & Vigouroux 1982).
- **2.6 Fires for management.** Prescribed burning is unlikely ever to be a safe option for urban trees

- **2.7 Species choice and impact on soils.** Urban tree species choice should be driven by experience and scientific information. There is therefore no reason to specifically favour native species or provenances (Johnston et al. 2011).
- **2.8 Pesticide use.** Use of pesticides is more restricted in built up areas than in conventional forestry, but the same priorities exist of: using pest-resistant varieties, maximising genetic variety of trees, conserving natural enemies of pests and use of selective pesticides (Dreistadt & Flint 2016; Wu et al. 1991). Pesticide injections can be used for high value trees, but is costly and time consuming.
- **2.11 Pesticide safety.** Restricted in build up areas.
- **2.12 Fertiliser use.** Growth of urban trees often stagnates because of site factors like drought or rise of groundwater. Root growth is often restricted and can lead to nutrient shortage. Soil and foliar analysis can
- **2.13 Good Agricultural Practice.** Best practice guides exist for urban parks and gardens (US National Park Service 2007)

Criterion 3 (productive functions of ToF).

- **3.1 Land Productivity.** See criteria 1. Trees generally restore fertility in degraded urban areas (Oldfield et al. 2015).
- **3.2 Economics.** Many studies are available of the economic value of urban trees²³ for pollution control, recreation, amenity, stormwater alleviation, microclimate improvement etc. (Rodgers et al. 2015), although these often neglect the potential value of the timber itself.
- **3.5 Sustainable Harvesting.** See requirement 1.9. Harvesting difficult because of public access, traffic and Health & Safety issues
- **3.6 Preservation of Soil Fertility.** See requirement 2.12
- **3.7 Non-timber products.** NTFPs can be important in urban and peri-urban woodlands, in temperate areas (Kilchling et al. 2009/7), but are mainly so in the tropics (Famuyide & Adebayo 2013).
- **3.8 Impact of infrastructure.** Infrastructure already exists, but harvesting operations often costly.

Criterion 4 (conservation and enhancement of biodiversity).

- **4.1 Biological and landscape diversity.** Species and habitat diversity are at a premium in urban areas, and the environmental services of trees have high economic and social value. (Platt et al. 1994; Tratalos et al. 2007; Alvey 2006)
- **4.2 Habitat conservation.** Many cities have surprisingly high urban tree canopy cover (Toronto 28%, Washington 29%, Pittsburg 35%, Annapolis 41%) which provides a vital opportunity to conserve wildlife habitats (Nowak et al. 2008).
- **4.3 Protected and endangered species.** Some urban tree habitats contain wild areas which host rare or endangered species, and should be included within urban management plans. Ecological studies have been conducted of many urban forests, sometimes in conjunction with local communities. (Chaparro & Terradas 2009)
- **4.4 Tree regeneration.** Natural regeneration can be prolific in urban forests although disturbance may favour some species more than others (Lehvāvirta & Rita 2002).
- **4.5 Native species and provenances.** There should not necessarily be a preference for native species, and the implications of climate change must now be considered (Roloff et al. 2009). See 2.7
- **4.6 Landscape connectivity.** Green corridors containing trees are particularly vital in cities for conservation of biodiversity (Vergnes et al. 2012/1).
- **4.7 Genetically Modified Organisms.** Urban and forest trees are suffering increasingly damaging attacks from pests and diseases. There may be an option to develop ortets of native tree species which are resistant to these attacks, following current best practices on biosafety (Vettori et al. 2016; Ramawat et al. 2014).

²³ 8.4 million trees, tree cover 14%, tree and shrub cover 21%, pollution removal value 126.1 million, stormwater alleviation 2.1 m, carbon storage 4.79 m/ yr.

- **4.8 Landscape structural diversity.** Urban trees should be managed to preserve uneven age structures and a diverse canopy structure and make an important contribution to aesthetic value of urban landscapes (Ozkan & Ozdemir 2015).
- **4.9 Traditional management systems.** Hedgerows are sometimes retained in urban and peri-urban areas and traditional management will assist biodiversity conservation. Pollarding is frequent.
- **4.11 Infrastructure planning.** Road infrastructure will exist already.
- **4.12 Relic vegetation.** Old trees urban trees are less likely to be preserved than in the forest because of safety concerns.

Criterion 5: (protective functions of ToF).

- **5.1 Protective functions.** Urban trees have vital roles for climate regulation (Vailshery et al. 2013), air quality improvement (Garrec 1999; Nowak et al. 2006), aesthetics and cultural services (Salmond et al. 2016) and (in some locations) protect against erosion and landslides (Forbes & Broadhead 2013).
- **5.2 Identification of areas with special functions.** Most cities have structural plans and identification of existing trees. Major tree planting programmes in cities should involve local communities as much as possible and be well integrated with existing frameworks for management (Pincetl et al. 2012).
- **5.3 Areas of sensitive soil.** Urban trees reduce erosion when planted along streams and waterways (Dwyer et al. 1992)
- **5.4 Areas for water protection.** Urban trees can be planted and managed to improve stormwater management (Breen et al. 2004; Davey Resource Group 2013).
- **5.5 Infrastructure planning.** City planning should retain existing trees and streamside vegetation where possible and identify areas where trees are most needed (Portland State University 2016)

Criterion 6 (other socio-economic functions and conditions)

- **6.1 Multiple functions of trees.** More quantification is needed on multiple socio-economic benefits of urban forestry - e.g. consumer behaviour, inward investment, property values, crime reduction, health and exercise, pollution interception, carbon sequestration, energy regulation in buildings, noise reduction, hydrology, wildlife habitats, road safety, road surface conservation (Warwick District Council 2016).
- **6.3 Property & tenure rights.** Countries and cities differ widely in the protection afforded to urban trees (Profous & Loeb 1990). Not all trees are protected: usually the city authority will protect trees on an individual basis. Street trees may be damaged by trenching operations but it is difficult to attribute blame for any resulting death of trees (Jim 2003).
- **6.5 Recreation & amenity.** A methods are available to estimate the amenity of urban trees. The Helliwell system is based on expert judgement and has low data requirements (Helliwell 2008). The Capital Asset Value for Amenity Trees system (CAVAT) estimated the replacement cost of a tree and adjusts this using factors related to the tree's health, amenity and social value (Neilan 2009). The i-Tree system uses tree inventory data to quantify the monetary value of annual environmental and aesthetic benefits - i.e. energy conservation, air quality improvement, CO2 reduction, stormwater control, and property value increases . It allows users to answer management questions related to their urban tree programmes (USDA Forest Service 2016b; Rogers et al. 2011) .
- **6.6 Sites of cultural significance.** These sites will be recognised within the urban tree management plan.
- **6.7 Account for socio-economic services.** See 6.5, especially the i-Tree system.
- **6.8 Train managers and owners in multi-use options.** A number of best practice guides are available for managers of urban trees and forests (McGauley et al. 2000; Byrne & Sipe 2010; Watson 2014; Miller 2007).
- **6.9 Utilize local knowledge.** Public participation in urban forestry is possible at all stages of design, establishment, monitoring and maintenance (FAO/ECE/ILO 2000).
- **6.10 Involve local stakeholders.** A wider range of stakeholders are involved in the management of urban and peri-urban trees (Lawrence & Johnston 2011).
- **6.11 Health & Safety.** See 6.8

- **6.14 Participatory research.** Urban forestry research is often best planned and conducted in conjunction with local communities (Wolf & Kruger 2010; Wilmsen 2005; Van Herzele et al. 2005).

Criterion 7 (Compliance with legal requirements).

- **7.1 Comply with legislation.** See 6.3
- **7.2 Avoid illegal activities.** See 6.3

7 CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The FAO definition of “forest”, with a single global 10% crown-cover threshold, is useful for international comparative statistics, but is not appropriate for finer scale determination of the extent or volume of “Trees Outside Forests”. Adding the FAO category “Other Wooded Land” to statistics for ToF would increase the global assessment of ToF from 5.18% to 27.14% (related to total area covered by “tree-based systems” greater than 0.5 ha in size). ***Recommendation 1 (short term): PEFC should suggest to FAO that they consider changing their definition of Trees outside Forests to include Other Wooded Land.***
2. The FAO definition of “forest” excludes land that is “**predominantly** under agricultural land use”, and guidelines suggest that this land (providing that has more than 10% crown cover, and minimum area >0,5ha) should be classed as Other Land with Tree Cover (OLTC). Yet only 78 of 234 countries report this land use category. De Foresta et al (2013) noted this and made five recommendations: a) improving national OLTC assessments, b) clarifying the future role of the FAO-FRA in these assessments, c) refining the terminology used in the FRA, d) increasing the number of countries reporting OLTC, e) using the FAO FRA Remote Sensing Survey to develop a Global OLTC/ToF assessment. ***Recommendation 2 (short term) PEFC should ask the FAO to give their views on the conclusions of the de Foresta report, particularly relating to more comprehensive ToF reporting in Forest Resource Assessment 2020.***
3. Following the UNFCCC COP-21 in December 2015, many more parties will report annually or biannually on greenhouse gas emissions from Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU). They will be required to categorise all their land into six categories: forest, cropland, grazing-land, settlements, wetlands and other. Parties will be required to clarify their own national definitions of “forest” to the UNFCCC secretariat (defined in terms of potential tree height in situ, crown-cover and minimum area). Parties which include AFOLU in their National Determined Contributions (NDCs) will be required to estimate the impact of ToF on greenhouse gas emissions from non-forest land. ***Recommendation 3 (long-term): the PEFC could encourage FAO and the UNFCCC to coordinate their guidelines on quantifying the boundary between forest land and agricultural land, and provide assistance to non-Annex-I countries who have committed to reporting GHG emissions from Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) — including Trees outside Forests — as part of their UNFCCC Nationally Determined Contributions.***
4. Many UNFCCC Annex I parties will move to very-high-resolution reporting of emission levels based on GIS systems showing individual land parcels, and their land use. These land use systems are often linked to cadastral databases of land ownership, and could provide data for landowners to manage tree-resources on cropland or grazing-land. ***Recommendation 4 (short-term): PEFC should commission a report on efforts currently underway in UNFCCC Annex I countries to quantify the GHG emissions in Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) (including trees in agroforestry and settlements), and the potential use of the area data by managers of ToF.***
5. A set of generic criteria and requirements for sustainable management of ToF has been provided, making only modest changes in the existing PEFC SFM Meta-standard, with additions to refer to a)

Good Agricultural Practice standards, b) carbon sequestration and GHG emissions, c) the role of urban trees in air pollution control. **Recommendation 5 (short-term): obtain the view of PEFC Working Group on whether a ToF standard should be developed, or whether is a single standard is appropriate for all Tree Based Systems (i.e. forests, agroforests, urban trees).**

6. Draft Guidelines and literature references have been provided to aid implementation of the generic meta-standard in agroforestry and urban tree systems. In terms of UNFCCC reporting this would be on the “Cropland Management”, “Grazing-land Management”, and “Settlement Management” categories of land. In the case of agroforestry separate Guidelines are given for UNFCCC Annex 1 and non-Annex 1 parties. Both sets of Guidelines need expansion and refinement. **Recommendation 6 (medium-term): PEFC should work with others to refine the “Guidelines for Interpretation of the ToF sustainable management meta-standard” — possibly transposing it to wiki format — for agroforestry and urban tree systems in both UNFCCC Annex I and non-Annex I countries.**
7. Lack of formal land tenure is a major impediment to implementing sustainable management of tree-based systems in the tropics. **Recommendation 7 (short term): PEFC ToF pilot studies could be asked to focus on options to overcome tenure constraints, for example by low overhead “formalisation” of traditional land titles, particularly for trees outside the forest.**

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9 ANNEX A: Good Agricultural Practices

While management of trees in agroforestry systems must include issues of soil, water and environmental sustainability, it is outside the scope of the meta-standard to define good agricultural practices. These are discussed in a number of FAO and US publications (Poisot et al. 2007; USDA 2016; Hobbs 2003). In the EU, a list of “Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions” (GAEC) are set in Annex II of EU Regulation 1306/2013 (Table 6), which controls eligibility for basic payments and which Member States (MS) transpose into their national regulations (Angileri et al. 2011). GAEC-7 is particularly important for agroforestry as it provides MS with the option of declaring trees in line, in groups or as isolated trees to be “Landscape Features”. These trees (along with “permanent crop” trees like fruit trees and short-rotation coppice) will not count towards the tree-density or crown-density thresholds which determine whether a parcel is declared “agriculture” and therefore eligible direct payments.

Table 6: Extract from Regulation 1306/2013 (Annex II)... “Rules on Cross-Compliance” (European Commission 2013b)

Requirements and Standards	
Water	SMR1: Comply with Directive 91/676/EEC concerning protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources)
	GAEC 1: Establishment of buffer strips along water courses
	GAEC 2: Where use of water for irrigation is subject to authorisation, compliance with authorisation procedures
	GAEC 3: Protection of ground water against pollution: prohibition of direct discharge into groundwater and measures to prevent indirect pollution of groundwater through discharge on the ground and percolation through the soil of dangerous substances, as listed in the Annex to Directive 80/68/EEC in its version in force on the last day of its validity, as far as it relates to agricultural activity
Soil and carbon stock	GAEC 4: Minimum soil cover
	GAEC 5: Minimum land management reflecting site specific conditions to limit erosion
	GAEC 6: Maintenance of soil organic matter level through appropriate practices including ban on burning arable stubbles, except for plant health reasons
Biodiversity	SMR2: Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds
	SMR 3: Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild flora and fauna
Landscape	GAEC 7: Retention of landscape features, including where appropriate, hedges, ponds, ditches, trees in line, in group or isolated, field margins and terraces, and including a ban on cutting hedges and trees during the bird breeding and rearing season and, as an option, measures for avoiding invasive plant species
Plant Protection Products	SMR 10: Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of 21 October 2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market

10 ANNEX B: Additional Information on minimal tree strip widths for inclusion in national forest inventories [303].

Member state	Crown cover (%)	Minimum area (ha)	Height (m)	Minimal width (m)
Croatia, Poland	10	0.1	2	10m for Poland
Bulgaria, Germany	10	0.1	5	
Romania, (Southern) Finland	10	0.25	5	20
Italy, Luxembourg	10	0.5	5	
Denmark, (Northern) Finland, France, Sweden	10	0.5	5	20 (10m for Sweden)
Portugal	10	1	5	20
Ireland, Latvia	20	0.1	5	20
United Kingdom	20	0.1	2	20
Slovakia	20	0.3	5	
Belgium, Netherlands	20	0.5	5	30m for Netherlands
Spain	20	1	3	25
Greece	25	0.3	2	
Lithuania	30	0.1	5	10
Slovenia	30	0.25	2	
Czech Republic, Estonia	30	0.5	2	20m for Czech Republic
Hungary	30	0.5	5	10
Austria	30	0.05	2	10

11 ANNEX C: Draft Terms and Definitions

(Some standard PEFC definitions have been included together with those specific to this document):

Accredited certificate. A certificate issued by a Certification Body within the scope of its accreditation which bears the accreditation body's symbol.

Agroforestry. *ICRAF definition:* "The deliberate growing of woody perennials on the same unit of land as agricultural crops and/or animals, either in some form of spatial mixture or sequence" (Lundgren 1982). *EU Definition:* "Land use systems in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land. The minimum and maximum number of trees per hectare shall be determined by the Member States taking account of local pedo-climatic and environmental conditions, forestry species and the need to ensure sustainable agricultural use of the land." Article 23 of Regulation 1305/2013 (European Commission 2013c). *USDA Definition:* Agroforestry is the intentional integration of trees and shrubs into crop and animal farming systems to create environmental, economic, and social benefits (USDA 2011).

Certified material Raw material which is covered by the chain of custody claims. *Note: The criteria for certified material and its suppliers are defined as a part of the definition of PEFC claim(s) which can be found in an Appendix to this standard. In addition, forest certification schemes endorsed by PEFC can make their own definition of certified material for the purposes of their own claims applied together with this standard.*

Certified product. Product which is claimed as including certified material whose content is verified by chain of custody.

Chain of custody of forest based products. Process of handling of information on the material category of forest based products which allows the organisation to make accurate and verifiable claims on the content of certified material.

Conflict timber. "Timber that has been traded at some point in the chain of custody by armed groups, be they rebel factions or regular soldiers, or by a civilian administration involved in armed conflict or its representatives, either to perpetuate conflict or take advantage of conflict situations for personal gain... conflict timber is not necessarily illegal" or the exploitation of timber may itself be a direct cause of conflict. (Definition used by UNEP (<http://www.unep.org/dewa/Africa/publications/AEO-2/content/205.htm>)).

Controlled sources. Material for which the risk of originating from controversial sources has been minimized through the implementation of the PEFC Due Diligence System.

Controversial sources. Forest activities which are: (a) not complying with local, national or international legislation, applying to forest related activities, in particular in the following areas: forestry operations and harvesting, including biodiversity conservation and conversion of forest to other use; management of areas with designated high environmental and cultural values; protected and endangered species, including requirements of CITES; health and labour issues relating to forest workers, indigenous peoples' property, tenure and use rights, third parties' property, tenure and use rights, payment of taxes and royalties; (b) not complying with legislation of the country of harvest relating to trade and customs, in so far as the forest sector is concerned, (c) utilising genetically modified forest based organisms, (d) converting forest to other vegetation type, including conversion of primary forests to forest plantations. *Note: The policy on the exclusion of material from genetically modified forest based organisms remains in force until 31st December 2022.*

Cross compliance is a European Union mechanism that links direct payments to compliance by farmers with basic standards concerning the environment, food safety, animal and plant health and animal welfare, as well as the requirement of maintaining land in *Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition*.

Customer. A single entity, either buyer or user of the organisation's products, to whom the claim is made. *Note: The term "customer" also covers an internal customer within the organisation where more subsequent product groups exist.*

Due Diligence System (DDS). A framework of procedures and measures, namely information gathering, risk assessment and risk mitigation, to exercise due diligence (add ref to the PEFC Standard).

Forest. *FAO definition* "Land spanning more than 0.5 hectares with trees higher than 5 metres and a canopy cover of more than 10 percent; or trees able to reach these thresholds in situ. Does not include land that is predominantly agricultural or under urban land use" (FAO 2015a).

Forest based material. Raw material originating in forest areas or from other areas recognised by the PEFC Council as eligible for PEFC forest management certification, including recycled material originally coming from those areas. *Note: Forest based material includes wood based as well as non-wood based material.*

Forest based products. Products which include forest based material.

Forest plantation/timber plantation/productive plantation. Forest or other wooded land of introduced species, and in some cases native species, established through planting or seeding mainly for production of wood or non-wood goods. *Note 1: Includes all stands of introduced species established for production of wood or non-wood goods. Note 2: May include areas of native species characterised by few species, intensive land preparation (e.g. cultivation), straight tree lines and/or even-aged stands. Note 3: Application of the definition requires consideration of national forestry terminology and legal requirements.*

Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) are specific methods which, when applied to agriculture, create food for consumers or further processing that is safe and wholesome and agricultural systems which are sustainable. There are several broadly accepted schemes which producers can adhere to: e.g. FAO (ref), USDA (ref), EurepGAP (ref), GlobalGAP (ref), FarmAssurance (ref)

Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC) are defined in the framework of EU “cross-compliance”. In order to ensure that all agricultural land, especially land which is no longer used for production purposes, is maintained in good agricultural and environmental conditions, Member States must define minimum requirements on the basis of Annex II of Council Regulation (EC) No 1306/2013. GAECs requirements should be defined taking into account the specific characteristics of the areas concerned, including soil and climatic condition, existing farming systems, land use, crop rotation, farming practices and farm structures. The following GAECs are relevant to agroforestry: 1, establishment of buffer zones along water courses; 2, water used for irrigation is subject to authorisation; 3, protection of groundwater against pollution; 4, maintenance of minimum soil cover; 5, land management to reflect specific conditions to limit erosion; 6, maintenance of soil organic matter through appropriate practices including ban on burning arable stubbles (except for plant health reasons); 7, retention of landscape features (hedges, ponds, ditches, trees in line, in group or isolated, field margins and terraces, ban on cutting hedges in bird breeding season and measures to avoid invasive species. Additionally there are Specific Management Requirements in relation to key EU Environmental Regulations.

Labelling. Usage of labels (on- or off-product).

Land Management Unit (LMU). Homogeneous areas of land, within a larger area, which have similar management requirements and respond in a similar way to management, irrespective of ownership considerations. This is a term mainly used in the USA and Australia .. it risks confusion with “Land Ownership Unit” and is better renamed .. or ignored?

Land Ownership Unit. An aggregation of Land Parcels which are managed as a whole and may be subject to a Management Plan.

Parcel. In real estate, a lot or plot is a tract or parcel of land owned or meant to be owned by some owner(s).

Land Parcel Identification System. A term largely used in developed countries for a geospatial database which records details of farmers fields (physical and actual parcels), land use, land cover and environmental features like trees. *Note 1.* There is usually a parcel by parcel differentiation of “forest land” from “agricultural land. The LPIS is often linked to a national land register (cadastre) for tax and ownership purposes. In the EU, from 2016, orthophotos will be held with a 1:5000 resolution (i.e. 50cm pixels). *Note 2.* In the EU farmers receive direct payments only for “agricultural land” although payments will be reduced, following national or regional rules, depending on tree crown-cover, slope, bare ground etc. *Note 3.* Where a national or regional LPIS exists, there is a strong case for this being used at the definitive record of “agricultural” or “forest” land since it will be the most accurate and “legal” classification.

Land Use Land-use Change and Forestry (LULUCF). A greenhouse gas inventory sector that covers emissions and removals of greenhouse gases resulting from direct human-induced land use, land-use change and forestry activities (Lulucf 2003). Replaced in the IPCC AR3 (2007) by AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use) which for the first time presents guidelines from the reporting of emissions and fluxes of GHGs from the terrestrial land surface using a single set of methodologies (Smith et al. 2014). Not all countries have followed these suggested methodological changes, and the EU, for example, continues to talk of LULUCF (European Commission, DG CLIMA n.d.). Importantly for these Guidelines, countries must make separate returns of net emissions for Forest Land (including Forest Management - FM) and Agricultural Land (including Crop Management - CM, and Grazing Management GM). Trees outside the Forest would be included in CM and GM.

Management Plans (or equivalent instruments). A operational plan for a forest, agroforest or urban-forest management unit which usually defines a) the landowner goals and objectives, b) the location and parcel map, c) the existing timber and land resource and expected increment, d) planned protection and maintenance activities, e) enhancement of environmental services, f) public access considerations.. The format will vary depending on the size of the holding and the type of forest, agroforest or urban-forest. Countries vary considerably in their expectations for the production of management plans, and recent survey of requirements has been undertaken by the European Union (DG Environment 2013)

Material category. The characteristics of the place where the raw material is coming from. Note: This standard uses three material categories: certified, neutral and other material, whose definitions are made specifically for individual claims.

Neutral material. Material which is not forest-based and is therefore considered as neutral in the calculation of the certification percentage. Note: Forest certification schemes endorsed by PEFC can make their own definition of neutral material within their own claims used together with this standard.

Organisation. Any entity which is making claims on products and is implementing the requirements of this standard. Such an entity has the ability to clearly identify the supplier of its raw materials and the customer of its products.

Other Land with Tree Cover. An FAO land category in which land that is not classified as “Forest” or “Other wooded land” which has predominantly agricultural or urban land uses and has patches of tree cover that span more than 0.5 hectares with a canopy cover of more than 10 percent of trees able to reach a height of 5 meters at maturity. It includes both forest and non-forest tree species.

Other Wooded Land (OWL). Land not defined as “Forest”, spanning more than 0.5 hectares; with trees higher than 5 meters and a canopy cover of 5-10 percent, or trees able to reach these thresholds; or with a combined cover of shrubs, bushes and trees above 10 percent. It does not include land that is predominantly under agricultural or urban land use (FAO 2015a). The FAO often reports these areas together with “Forest”.

Other material. Forest based material other than certified material.

PEFC recognised certificate is: (a) a valid accredited forest management certificate issued by a PEFC notified certification body against the forest management scheme/standard which is endorsed by the PEFC Council, (b) a valid accredited chain of custody certificate issued by a PEFC notified certification body against this standard together with PEFC recognised specification of the material category, or © a valid accredited chain of custody certificate issued by a PEFC notified certification body against a scheme specific chain of custody standard which is endorsed by the PEFC Council. Note: PEFC endorsed forest certification schemes and chain of custody standards are found at the PEFC Council website, www.pefc.org.

Physical separation. A procedure in which various materials/products of different material categories are kept separate so that the category of the material/products used and transferred to the customer is known. Note: Physical separation can involve physical separation at an organisation's facility e.g. in separate bays or in specific storage areas of the facility, or it can include clear marking or usage or having distinguishing marks, to readily identify the materials of different origin categories.

Primary forest. Forest of native species where there are no clearly visible indications of human activities and the ecological processes are not significantly disturbed. Note: Includes areas where collection of non-timber forest products occurs, provided the human impact is small. Some trees may have been removed.

Product group. Set of products manufactured or traded in the specified processes which are covered by the organisation's chain of custody. Note 1: The organisation can establish one or more product groups as a result of parallel or subsequent processes. Note 2: The chain of custody product group can also include a single product for which the chain of custody is implemented. This approach of implementing chain of custody is also called "project chain of custody".

Recycled material. Forest based material that is (a) diverted from the waste stream during a manufacturing process. Excluded is reutilisation of materials such as rework, regrind or scrap generated in a process and capable of being reclaimed within the same process that generated it. Excluded are by-products such as sawmilling by-products (sawdust, chips, bark, etc.) or forestry residues (bark, chips from branches, roots, etc.) as they do not represent "waste stream". (b) generated by households or by commercial, industrial and institutional facilities in their role as end-users of the product which can no longer be used for its intended purpose. This includes returns of material from the distribution chain. Note 1: The term "capable of being reclaimed within the same process that generated it" means that the material generated in one process is continuously returned to the same process at the same site. An example is residue generated by a press line in a panel board production which continuously re-enters the same press line. This is not considered as recycled material. Note 2: Material classified under the grades of recovered paper according to EN 643 is recognised as meeting the definition of the recycled material. Note 3: The definition is based on definitions of ISO 14021:1999

Rolling percentage calculation. Calculation of the certification percentage based on input material procured during the specified period before the product's manufacturing or trading.

Simple percentage calculation. Calculation of the certification percentage based on input material physically included in the product for which the calculation is made. Note: An example of the simple percentage calculation is a printing job where the certification percentage is calculated from the material purchased and used for this specific printing job.

Supplier. A clearly identified single entity directly supplying input material to the relevant product group. Note 1: In cases where the material is physically delivered by another entity than that having the ownership title to the material, the organisation shall appoint a single supplier for the purposes of this definition, either an entity with the ownership title or an entity physically delivering the material. E.g. A printing house procuring material from a distributor, which is however delivered directly by a paper producer, may consider as the supplier either the distributor or paper producer. Note 2: The term supplier also covers an internal supplier within the organisation where more subsequent product groups exist.

Sustainable Management takes the concepts from sustainability and synthesizes them with the concepts of [management](#). [Sustainability](#) has three branches: the [environment](#), the needs of present and future generations, and the [economy](#). Using these branches, it creates the ability to keep a system running indefinitely without depleting resources, maintaining economic viability, and also nourishing the needs of the present and future generations. From this definition, sustainable management has been created to be defined as the application of sustainable practices in the categories of [businesses](#), [agriculture](#), [society](#), environment, and personal life by managing them in a way that will benefit current generations and future generations (source Wikipedia).

Accuracy of Monitoring. IPCC methods involve 3 tiers (or approaches) to define the land use units used in GHG calculations and three tiers of accuracy in defining the emissions from each land use unit.

Tree Certification. Often with ToF, trees and timber production are a minority product of the land use system, which focuses on food in the case of agroforestry or recreation and amenity in the case of urban-forestry. It may not be appropriate therefore to certify the sustainability of the whole system, and may be sufficient to ensure that the management of the tree component matches appropriate PEFC guidelines. This approach does however require the Chain of Custody to include details of the land management unit from which the timber originated (in contrast to Chain of Custody approach).

Trees Outside the Forest. "Trees on land not defined as 'forest and other wooded land', including: trees on land that fulfils the requirements of forest and other wooded land except that the area is less than 0.5 ha; trees able to reach a height of at least 5 m at maturity in situ where the stocking level is below 5 percent; trees not able to reach a height of 5 m at maturity in situ where the stocking level is below 20%; scattered trees in permanent meadows and pastures; permanent tree crops such as fruit-trees and coconuts; trees in parks and gardens, around buildings and in lines along streets, roads, railways, rivers, streams and canals; trees in shelterbelts of less than 20 m width and 0.5 ha area." (Bellefontaine et al. 2002)

Urban Forestry is the management of trees for their contribution to the physiological, sociological, and economic well-being of urban society. Urban forestry deals with woodlands, groups of trees, and individual trees, where people live - it is multifaceted, for urban areas include a great variety of habitats (streets, parks, derelict corners, etc) where trees bestow a great variety of benefits and problems (Carter 1993).

12. ANNEX D Change Log

1. Changes to be made including reference to the the paper in Proc Roy Soc B. ([Ahrends et al. 2017](http://rspb.royalsocietypublishing.org/content/royprsb/284/1854/20162559.full.pdf))
<http://rspb.royalsocietypublishing.org/content/royprsb/284/1854/20162559.full.pdf>
2. Also ([Chazdon et al. 2016](#)).
3. May need to add a comment on Switzerland to the effect that the National Forest Inventory defines forest as area of cover of trees over 3 m in height at least 50 m wide and with greater than 20% projected crown cover. With greater crown cover, a decrease in width of the treed area is allowed down to a minimum of 25 m at 100% crown cover (Brassel and Lischke 2001). This differs from the Kyoto Protocol definition used by Switzerland where a forest is a treed area wider than 25 m with more than 20% crown cover (FOEN 2016a).